

Valorisation of Phosphogypsum via Leaching: Evaluating Phosphorus and Calcium Separation

Thesis for M.Sc. in Chemical and Process Engineering

by

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Abstract

Title of the thesis: Valorisation of Phosphogypsum via Leaching: Evaluating Phosphorus and Calcium Separation

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Phosphogypsum (PG), a byproduct of phosphoric acid production, contains valuable elements such as phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), and rare earth elements (REE). However, it is largely landfilled, posing environmental risks and wasting recoverable resources. This study, conducted within the EU-funded FIC-Fighters project, aims to develop sustainable valorisation strategies by selectively separating P and Ca to produce an ultrapure gypsum phase suitable for CaCO₃ synthesis, while enabling P recovery.

Leaching experiments were carried out on two PG types: one from Finland, derived from magmatic phosphate ore, and one from Croatia, derived from sedimentary ore. Leaching experiments were conducted using acidic and basic solvents (HCl, H₂SO₄, citric acid, NH₃ and NH₄Cl) at concentrations of 0.1 M and 1 M with L/S ratios of 100, 50, 20 and 10 ml/g. Analytical techniques included UV-Vis spectroscopy, EDTA titration, ICP-OES and SEM-EDS, to quantify Ca and P and assess method reliability. Reproducibility of the experiments was validated by performing a set of experiments in triplicate.

Results showed that higher L/S ratios significantly enhanced the dissolution and recovery of both P and Ca. Elevated temperatures also improved dissolution, though additional research is needed to validate these results. Across all experiments, 1 M solvents consistently outperformed their 0.1 M counterparts. The origin of the PG had

a negligible impact on the recovery trends, indicating comparable behaviour across phosphate ore types. The highest recovery rates were achieved with 1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, though co-dissolution limited selective separation. NH₄Cl demonstrated potential for selective Ca recovery with reduced P solubility. However, co-dissolution levels remained too high.

Among analytical methods, ICP-OES proved the most versatile, while UV-Vis and EDTA titration offered cost-effective options for routine analysis, depending on sample composition. Although REE recovery was not assessed, future research should explore their potential, alongside further optimisation of HCl and NH₄Cl systems. Overall, these findings highlight the potential of tailored solvent systems for sustainable PG treatment and resource recovery.

Keywords: *Phosphogypsum, valorisation, phosphorus recovery, calcium separation, selective leaching, sustainable resource recovery, circular economy*

Preface

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Abbreviations

A	Absorbance
APHA	American Public Health Association
BSE	Backscattered electrons
c	Concentration
CrG	Croatian phosphogypsum
CA	Citric acid
EBT	Eriochrome Black T
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
ϵ	Molar absorptivity
FG	Finnish phosphogypsum
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICP-OES	Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy
K_{MeY}	Stability constant
L	Path length of radiation
L/S	Liquid-to-solid
MB	Molybdenum blue
MPG	Magmatic phosphogypsum
MT	Metric tonnes
NORM	Naturally occurring radioactive material
PCC	Precipitated calcium carbonate
PG	Phosphogypsum
REE	Rare earth elements
RPM	Revolutions per minute
SE	Secondary electrons
SEM-EDS	Scanning electron microscope with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
SPG	Sedimentary phosphogypsum
STD	Standard deviation
T	Transmittance
UV-Vis	Ultraviolet and visible light
V	Volume
Wt%	Weight percentage
ÅAU	Åbo Akademi University

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1 Introduction

Phosphogypsum (PG) is an industrial byproduct generated during the production of phosphate fertilisers. It is produced through wet digestion of natural phosphate rock with sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) for phosphoric acid production. PG is a heterogeneous substance, containing several valuable compounds such as calcium (Ca), sulphates, silicates, and phosphorus (P). PG also contains small amounts of rare earth elements (REE) alongside toxic elements such as heavy metals. Approximately five tons of PG is generated per ton of phosphoric acid produced, resulting in an estimated annual production of 100-280 million tons of PG (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009; Yang *et al.*, 2009).

PG is currently disposed of in landfills without prior treatment, posing significant environmental challenges for the phosphate industry. Erosion of PG piles and the release of pollutants can lead to contamination of surrounding ecosystems. Valorising PG could mitigate these impacts (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009; Akfas *et al.*, 2024). Given that PG contains P, its recovery offers a sustainable strategy, especially as P is classified as a critical raw material by the EU (European Commission, 2014). With global phosphate rock reserves estimated at 74,000 million metric tons and expected to be depleted within 50-100 years (US Geological Survey, 2025), concerns over long-term availability are growing (Brownlie *et al.*, 2022).

On this matter, the FIC-Fighters project, an EU-funded initiative, focuses on valorising PG to produce sustainable raw materials, such as ultrapure calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), sodium sulphate (Na_2SO_4), ammonium sulphate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$), P and REE, for use in industries including paper, cement, battery, fertiliser and detergents. Achieving ultrapure CaCO_3 requires the removal or separation of impurities in PG, such as P, REEs and radioactive elements, which present opportunities to recover these components as valuable products (*FIC Fighters Webpage*, 2025). At Åbo Akademi University (ÅAU), PG is converted into CaCO_3 in an ammoniacal medium, using carbon dioxide (CO_2), simultaneously generating a byproduct stream of ammonium sulphate. This byproduct can be further separated into reusable ammonium (NH_4^+) and H_2SO_4 , which may be repurposed in other industrial processes (Mattila and Zevenhoven, 2015). However, the final product remains contaminated, making

selective separation of key elements essential. This thesis focuses on evaluating a separation route for P, aiming to produce a clean intermediate suitable for carbonisation in the subsequent process developed by ÅAU. Due to time constraints and the lack of available analytical methods, REE leachability was not assessed in this study.

1.1 Aim of this work

The primary aim of this thesis is to evaluate the separation of P and Ca from two distinct PG sources, one sedimentary and one magmatic. The distribution of P and Ca under varying leaching conditions, using commonly available acids and bases, was systematically investigated. The objective is to extract significant amounts of P while generating a Ca-rich intermediate suitable for subsequent carbonisation. This purification step not only enables the valorisation of the cleaned gypsum but also facilitates the recovery of P, contributing to more sustainable resource utilisation. Additionally, a range of analytical techniques was employed to quantify Ca and P, to determine the most reliable and cost-effective method for routine analysis based on the obtained results.

2 Literature review

2.1 Phosphogypsum

PG is an industrial waste product generated during the production of phosphoric acid. The production of PG and phosphoric acid occurs through the digestion of phosphate rock, a concentrated slurry of pulverised phosphate ores, using H_2SO_4 at a temperature of typically 75-80°C (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009; Li, Malik and Azimi, 2022). The process described, known as “wet digestion”, accounts for approximately 90% of the worldwide phosphoric acid production. For every ton of phosphoric acid produced, about 4.5-5.5 tons of PG is generated, resulting in an estimated annual production of 100 to 280 million tonnes (Yang *et al.*, 2009; Binnemans *et al.*, 2013). The chemical reaction for this process is shown in Eq. (1).

In addition to the wet method, phosphoric acid can also be produced through pyrometallurgical methods. This process involves the thermal reduction of phosphate rock in an electric furnace to yield elemental phosphorus (Cánovas *et al.*, 2018). A general overview of the two processes is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. General scheme of the phosphate processes, adapted from USEPA, (1993)

2.1.1 Characterisation of phosphogypsum

PG is a predominantly crystalline, powdery material with negligible plasticity, consisting of mostly silt-sized, slightly aggregated gypsum crystals (Kacimi *et al.*, 2006). Its morphology is shaped by a combination of factors, including the origin and the particle size distribution in phosphate rock, the wet processing method used in the phosphoric acid production, the concentration of the acid, and the operational efficiency of the plant. Environmental conditions at the disposal site, such as age, location, and depth, also influence the physical structure and aggregation of the crystals (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009; Cánovas *et al.*, 2018). Based on these morphological and textural characteristics, PG can be classified into five distinct groups as illustrated in Figure 2. Group 1 consists of rhombic crystals with needle-like shapes ranging from 10 to 120 μm , whereas group 2 features fine agglomerated needles with a narrower size distribution, ranging between 5 and 30 μm . Group 3 is characterised by disorderly, aggregated crystals, group 4 by small, rounder grains, and group 5 by thin, elongated needle-shaped crystals. These morphological differences reflect variations in crystallisation conditions and the degree of aggregation during and after production (Bilal *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 2. SEM images of different PG types differentiated by morphology and texture. Rhombic type (Group 1), aggregate small rhombic type (Group 2), cluster type (Group 3), aggregate short needle type (Group 4) and needle type (Group 5) (Bilal *et al.*, 2023).

Although PG is primarily composed of crystalline gypsum, amorphous phases may also be present, particularly among the impurity fractions. These include poorly crystalline or non-crystalline forms of silica and organic matter, which may result from rapid precipitation, incomplete crystallisation, or the retention of unreacted materials during the phosphoric acid production. Amorphous fluorosilicates and calcium phosphates can also form under specific chemical conditions. These non-crystalline components are often embedded in the CaSO_4 matrix and can be hard to (Bourgier, C., 2007; Dai *et al.*, 2017).

The mineralogical composition of PG is dominated by gypsum, consisting of over 90% of it (Kacimi *et al.*, 2006). Chemically, gypsum is known as calcium sulphate, which, depending on the degree of hydration, can exist in three mineral phases: dihydrate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), hemihydrate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and anhydrite (CaSO_4) (Freyer and Voigt, 2003). Dihydrates are typically formed at temperatures between 70 and 80°C, while hemihydrates require temperatures above 90°C (Bilal *et al.*, 2023). In addition to gypsum, PG contains approximately 5% quartz, although this amount varies depending on the origin of the phosphate rock. Trace amounts of fluorapatite are also present, resulting from unreacted phosphate residues still present after acidic leaching during the phosphoric acid production (Rutherford, Dudas and Samek, 1994). European Fertilizer Manufacturers, (2000) presents mass fractions (%) of major elements found in phosphate rock of different origins, highlighting the compositional differences.

The chemical diversity of phosphate ores, combined with the capacity for ionic substitutions within their crystal lattices, facilitates the transfer of a wide range of elements into PG during the acidic leaching stage of phosphoric acid production. As a result, PG inherits a complex and variable composition that reflects both the mineralogical characteristics of the original ore, such as sedimentary phosphate rock (SPG) or magmatic phosphate rock (MPG), and the conditions of the processing method (Bourgier, 2007). Impurities in PG are generally classified into two categories: soluble and insoluble. Soluble impurities include salts or acids not removed during the filtration step. These are comprised of H_3PO_4 and calcium phosphates, which can react with Ca to form $\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. F is also incorporated into PG in the form of SiF_6^{2-} and F^- ions, which may combine with alkaline elements to form compounds such

as malladrite (Na_2SiF_6). Additionally, fluorides can precipitate as complex crystalline salts; fluorosilicate (H_2SiF_6) in solution and calcium fluoride (CaF_2). Together with H_2SO_4 these compounds contribute to the acidity of PG.

Table 1. Mass fraction (%) of major elements in phosphate rocks from various locations (European Fertilizer Manufacturers, 2000)

Mass fraction wt%	CEI-Russia*	South Africa-Phalaborwa*	Morocco-Khouribga	USA-Florida	Senegal	Togo
P_2O_5	38.9	36.8	33.4	34.3	36.7	36.7
CaO	50.5	52.1	50.6	49.8	50	51.2
SiO_2	1.1	2.6	1.9	3.7	5.0	4.0
F	3.3	2.2	4.0	3.9	3.7	3.8
CO_2	0.2	3.5	4.5	3.1	1.8	1.5
Al_3O_3	0.4	0.2	0.4	1.1	1.1	1.0
Fe_2O_3	0.3	0.3	0.2	1.1	0.9	1.0
MgO	0.1	1.1	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.1
Na_2O	0.4	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.3	0.2
K_2O	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
SO_3	0.1	0.2	1.6	0.1	-	0.3

* Magmatic

Trace elements in PG may be uniformly distributed within the crystal lattice or exist as distinct mineral phases. Their composition is also influenced by the origin of the phosphate rock, and some typical ranges are shown in Table 2. These trace elements include heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, zinc and copper (Bouargane, Pérez-Moreno, *et al.*, 2023). Apatite, the dominant mineral in most phosphate deposits, plays a vital role in the incorporation of REEs in PG. Variations in physical, chemical and crystallographic properties of apatite, such as lattice structure, ionic radius compatibility and substitution capacity, directly affect its ability to incorporate REEs into its crystal framework (McClellan and Van Kauwenbergh, 1991). During the production of phosphoric acid, these REEs are transferred from the phosphate rock into the resulting PG. Consequently, the concentration of REEs in PG is intricately linked to the type of phosphate rock used. MPG tends to have higher concentrations of REEs and Fluorine (F), and often produces PG with coarser, more crystalline textures. In contrast, SPG contain more silica and soluble impurities, resulting in PG with finer particles and higher levels of soluble P_2O_5 and trace elements (European Fertilizer Manufacturers, 2000; Binnemans *et al.*, 2015). These variations likely

originate from the broad chemical diversity inherent to phosphate ore types (Liu *et al.*, 2022).

Insoluble impurities make up a substantial portion of the total impurities and include poorly soluble minerals that remain unchanged during the phosphoric acid production. These consist of unreacted apatite, fluorite, silica, organic carbon, radioactive elements, and metals such as iron, selenium and magnesium (Lehr, Frazier and Smith, 1966). Impurities are often embedded in CaSO₄. Its low solubility contributes to the stability of these compounds and influences the leaching behaviour of incorporated metals (Dai *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2. Variations in trace elements (ppm) in phosphate rocks from various locations (European Fertilizer Manufacturers, 2000)

Trace elements (ppm)	CEI-Russia*	South Africa-Phalaborwa*	Morocco-Khouribga	USA-Florida	Senegal	Toho
Rare earth elements	6,200	4,800	900	600		
U ₃ O ₈	11	134	185	124		
As	10	13	13	11	18	12
Cd	1.2	1.3	15	9	53	53
Cr	19	1	200	60	6	
Cu	37	102	40	13		
Hg	33	0.1	0.1	0.02	0.2	0.6
Ni	2	2	35	28		
Pb		11	10	17	5	
Zn	20	6	200-400	70		

*Magmatic

2.1.2 Radiological characteristics of phosphogypsum

Phosphate ores are classified as a naturally occurring radioactive material, also referred to as a NORM residue. This is primarily due to the presence of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th. As shown in Fig.1, the wet digestion causes the selective separation of naturally occurring Radium (Ra), Uranium (U) and Thorium (Th), which are distributed between the phosphoric acid and the PG. Furthermore, a wide range of ²²⁶Ra concentrations has been observed, depending on the nature of the phosphate rock and the depth of sampling. These differences in concentration of NORM in P-rock are

illustrated in Table 3, which compares radionuclide concentrations in PG from various global sources (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009).

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) provides safety standards and guidance for industries handling NORM. They cover the importance of radiological protection, environmental stewardship and regulatory control throughout the lifecycle of a NORM residue (e.g. PG) (IAEA, 2014).

In the EU, PG management is governed by a directive, which sets basic safety standards for protection against ionising radiation. This directive requires members of the EU to regulate NORM residues such as PG, ensuring that reuse or disposal does not result in public or occupational exposures exceeding 1 mSv/year. Clearance levels for NORM are typically set around 0.3-0.4 Bq/g for natural decay series radionuclides, and up to 10 Bq/g for individual radionuclides (Wang *et al.*, 2018; EU-USHA, 2024).

Table 3. Radionuclides (Bq/kg) based on different origins of PG (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009)

Location	PG rock origin	²³⁸ U	²²⁶ Ra	²¹⁰ Pb	²¹⁰ Po	²³⁰ Th
Spain	Morocco	140	620		82	280
China	Keiyan	15	85	82	82	
Indonesia	PT Petrokimia					
	Gresik	43	473	480	450	
India	Vadorado	60	510	490	420	
Egypt	Nile Valley rock		100		445	
Florida	Central Florida	130	1140	1370	1030	113
Australia	Numerous	10	500			
Sweden	Kola	390	15			

2.2 Phosphogypsum environmental impact

The management of PG presents the most significant environmental challenge for the phosphate industry. Current management strategies involve surface disposal under unsaturated conditions or storage in water bodies under saturated conditions. These practices not only result in the loss of potential commercial benefits through missed opportunities for valorisation but also pose serious environmental concerns (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009; Akfas *et al.*, 2024). The disposal of untreated PG requires vast land areas

and can lead to contamination of soil, water, and the atmosphere. When arable land is repurposed for PG storage, it often becomes unsuitable for agricultural use (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

Landfilling of PG alters the natural landscape and disrupts the function of local soil ecosystems, while also diminishing the aesthetic value of the surrounding area. As such, PG storage sites are considered complex sources of environmental pollution and landscape degradation (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

The environmental impacts include erosion of PG piles and the release of harmful substances. This results from the emission of hazardous vapours containing heavy metals, sulphates, fluorosilicates, hydrogen fluoride, phosphorus, cadmium, and ^{226}Ra , all of which can negatively affect air quality (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009). Contamination may also spread to surrounding areas via atmospheric transport. For example, dust emitted from PG stacks can contain up to 10 g of fluorine per ton of PG. Fluoride compounds in this form are highly toxic to vegetation (Rutherford, Dudas and Samek, 1994).

Another environmental concern is the leachability of hazardous elements from PG, and thereby the contamination of groundwater beneath disposal sites. Because PG is often transported and deposited as an aqueous slurry, there is a risk of tidal fluctuations and leaching processes mobilising toxic substances. This entails risks in the dissolved elements being disposed of in nearby soils or transferred to waters, and also poses risks of transferring them to living beings (Reijnders, 2007). During precipitation, generated wastewater on the slopes holds up to 3.4 g/L P_2O_5 . This is over a hundred times higher than the natural content of phosphorus ions in the surface waters of humid zones (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

2.3 Valorisation routes for phosphogypsum

As previously mentioned, PG pose significant environmental challenges. Currently, only 15% of PG is being reused, while the remaining 85% is landfilled, often without treatment (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009). For example, Croatia, Kutina disposal site is estimated to contain about 8.5 Mt of CrG (Bituh *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the utilisation of PG is paramount to reduce its environmental footprint and promote sustainable resource use.

For this reason, various valorisation strategies have been developed. These approaches aim to recover valuable elements such as P and REEs, while also enabling applications such as CO₂ sequestration for Ca recovery.

2.3.1 P recovery from phosphogypsum

P is a vital nutrient for biological growth and a cornerstone of global agriculture, primarily through its use in phosphate-based fertilisers (Bindraban, Dimkpa and Pandey, 2020). With increasing demand and the projected depletion of natural phosphate ore reserves within the next 50-100 years (Brownlie *et al.*, 2022), recovering P from secondary sources such as PG has become a strategic priority for sustainable resource management.

Although PG is a by-product of phosphoric acid production, it retains approximately 2% of the original P₂O₅ content from the phosphate rock. This residual phosphorus exists both as water-soluble phosphates and structurally bound species within the gypsum matrix. The recovery of P from PG is most commonly achieved through leaching, a separation process in which a solid component is selectively dissolved into a solution, resulting in the formation of a solute component and an inert or less soluble solid residue. Depending on the application, either the dissolved solute, the residual solid, or both may be of interest. The efficiency of the leaching is dependent on several factors, including particle size, solvent type and concentration, temperature, intermolecular forces, and distribution. Sufficient contact time between solvent and solids, along with stable fluid flow, pressure, and temperature, is essential for effective leaching (Richardson, J.F.; Harker, J.H.; Backhurst, J.R., 2002).

According to a study by Dong *et al.* (2025), smaller PG particles increase surface area and enhance solute release, while Mashifana, Ntuli and Okonta (2019) reported that elevated temperature accelerated reaction kinetics. Although stirring speed has minimal impact, longer contact times generally enhanced P recovery. However, the improvement tends to plateau beyond a specific threshold, suggesting that shorter durations may suffice if other parameters are optimised, such as acid concentration and temperature are optimised. For example, leaching with 0.5 M citric acid (CA) at 40°C significantly increased P recovery, with conversion fractions rising from

approximately 0.7 to 0.95, compared to room temperature. Furthermore, utilising concentrations of 0.25 M, 0.5 M, and 0.75 M in combination with leaching times ranging from 2 to 24 hours demonstrated results, where negligible changes in P conversion were observed beyond 6 hours. Whereas a notable increase of 30% was observed between 4 and 6 hours, highlighting the importance of identifying optimal contact durations for efficient recovery (Mashifana, Ntuli and Okonta, 2019).

Among leaching agents, H_2SO_4 is widely used due to its strong acidity and compatibility with PG. However, its reuse in PG valorisation presents a challenge, as it promotes the formation of insoluble calcium sulphate (CaSO_4), which can trap phosphate species and reduce leaching efficiency (Dong *et al.*, 2025). Nevertheless, Shah *et al.* (2022) reported a P_2O_5 recovery rate of 59.06% after PG was treated with 4% H_2SO_4 for 2 hours.

CA offers an environmentally friendly alternative to mineral acids, achieving comparable recovery rates under similar conditions, without introducing hazardous by-products. Furthermore, it forms soluble calcium citrate complexes, avoiding the possible precipitation issue with H_2SO_4 (Shah *et al.*, 2022).

The mineralogical structure of PG also influences the leaching behaviour. Water-soluble phosphates can be removed by washing with water, whereas phosphate species such as HPO_4^{2-} and FPO_3^{2-} , which substitute for SO_4^{2-} ions in the PG crystal lattice, form solid compounds which are more resistant to dissolution. In addition to the leaching agents already mentioned, hot ammonia sulphate solution ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$), hydrochloric acid (HCl), and acetic acid (CH_3COOH) have also been proven to be effective solvents for separating P from PG (Shah *et al.*, 2022).

A more recent approach for P recovery from PG includes integrating ZrO_2 membrane triggered adsorption with struvite crystallisation, achieving an overall P recovery efficiency of approximately 60%. This method shows promise for recovering P from both G and PG-contaminated groundwater (Hu *et al.*, 2023). A study using a two-step approach involving acid leaching followed by electrochemical precipitation has also been researched. The approach was proven effective for recovering phosphate ions from PG. The reported efficiency was 99.3% (Liu *et al.*, 2025).

2.3.2 Ca recovery from phosphogypsum

Approximately 90-95% of PG consists of CaSO_4 (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009). Gypsum is a relatively stable mineral, and therefore, stronger acids or bases are required for effective dissolution (Bao *et al.*, 2017). In contrast to P, which typically exists as water-soluble phosphates in PG and can be mobilised under mildly acidic conditions, Ca recovery often requires stronger acids or bases for effective dissolution (Zhou *et al.*, 2024).

Hydrometallurgical valorisation of PG is gaining attention due to its potential economic and environmental benefits. These processes typically involve a sequence of steps, including sample pretreatment, characterisation, extraction of Ca and sulphate ions using aqueous solutions, and final product recovery. Commonly used chemical media include hydroxide-, carbonate-, chloride- and fluoride-based solutions (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023). These valorisation routes also allow the use of PG as a raw material for CO_2 mineral sequestration. Due to its high calcium content, dissolved Ca from PG can react with carbon dioxide to form stable CaCO_3 , effectively capturing and storing CO_2 , thus mitigating greenhouse gas emissions. Studies have shown that over 95% of PG can be carbonated with a reaction time exceeding one hour (Bao *et al.*, 2017).

Among hydroxide-based methods, two main routes have been identified: the alkali route and the ammoniacal route. These are currently being explored by the FIC-Fighters project, with research on the ammoniacal route conducted at ÅAU and the alkali route investigated at the University of Seville (Zevenhoven *et al.*, 2019). Both routes involve a two-step process: alkaline dissolution of PG followed by carbonation. In the first step, PG is reacted with an alkaline solution; typically, sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium hydroxide (KOH), or ammonium hydroxide (NH_3). This step produces calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), as shown in Eq. (2). In the second step, the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ formed acts as a reactive medium for the subsequent carbonation step, where it reacts with CO_2 to form CaCO_3 (Eq. (3)) (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023). This route not only enables CO_2 sequestration but also yields value-added CaCO_3 , which has various industrial applications, such as construction, paper and plastics industries (Bao *et al.*, 2017).

The ammoniacal route, developed at ÅAU, offers another approach to recover Ca from PG through CO₂ mineral sequestration. This method involves reacting PG with NH₃ and CO₂ to produce (NH₄)₂SO₄ and precipitated calcium carbonate (PPC). The process is design not only to recover Ca in the form of PCC but also to enable the recycling of ammonium sulphate. In the first step, PG reacts with CO₂ and NH₃, forming CaCO₃ and releasing ammonium and sulphate ions into the solution, as shown in Eq. (4). In the second step the ammonium and sulphate ions produced are recombined to form solid ammonium sulphate (Eq. (5)). The step is facilitated by membrane separation techniques, which allow for the efficient recovery and reuse of ammonium sulphate. The process also allows the possibility to produce PCC with a pre-selected crystallinity (Mattila and Zevenhoven, 2015; Zevenhoven *et al.*, 2019).

An alternative method involves carbonate conversion, where PG is treated with carbonate solutions in the presence of soluble sulphate salts, such as potassium sulphate (K₂SO₄) or sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄). This method is considered environmentally friendly, cost effective, and scalable (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023). The chemical reactions are shown in Eq. (6) and Eq. (7).

This method also enables recovery of the resulting CaCO₃ by filtration and drying at approximately 100°C. Furthermore, the byproducts such as (NH₄)₂SO₄ provides additional value, particularly in agriculture applications as a source of nitrogen and sulphur for plant nutrition (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023).

The chloride- based conversion process can also be used where a chloride aqueous solution is used to produce sulphate salts from PG. This route often involves selective crystallisation using additives such as ammonia or isopropanol to isolate the desired salt products. However, a significant challenge with the process is the difficulty separating mixed salts, which complicates product purity and process efficiency (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023).

Zhou *et al.* (2024) demonstrated an efficient method for Ca recovery by first dissolving PG in NaOH, followed by BaCO₃ precipitation. This approach achieved nearly complete Ca extraction, with a reported Ca recovery rate of 99.9%. Furthermore, the process allowed the leaching solution to be reused for up to five cycles.

2.3.3 REE recovery from phosphogypsum

Despite extensive research, no method has yet proven economically viable for REE recovery from PG. This is primarily due to the low REEs concentrations found in PG (Brückner, Elwert and Schirmer, 2020). Nevertheless, several leaching strategies have shown promise. Such as leaching with inorganic acids; H₂SO₄, HNO₃ and HCl or leaching with organic solvents, including extractants such as 2-thenolytrifluoroacetone (HTTA), tributyl-phosphate (TBP), trioctyl-phosphine oxide (TOPO) and kerosene, which have demonstrated improved selectivity and reduced acid consumption in comparison to the inorganic acids (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023).

El-Didamony *et al.* (2013) reported that a leaching process using 0.7 M TBP and 0.9 M TOPO, at 55°C for two hours achieved a REE extraction rate of 70.4%. When combined with a pre-treatment step, which included washing with a hot 0.5 M Na₂CO₃ solution for one hour the resulting REE extraction was 80.1%. Gasser *et al.* (2022) summarises numerous studies that used acids such as CA, H₂SO₄, HNO₃, and HCl for REE extraction from PG, with recovery rates ranging from 50% to 90%, depending on variables such as acid concentration, temperature, and leaching duration. Additionally, Shahbaz (2022) reported on studies involving alkaline and salt-based leaching agents, including NaOH, NH₄Cl, and KOH, which achieved leaching efficiencies from moderate levels up to 90%.

Pre-treatment steps such as saline water washing and carbonate treatment improve leaching efficiency by removing water-soluble impurities and forming a calcite phase, which enhances REE recovery in acidic conditions. Subsequently separation and purification steps are necessary to isolate high-purity REEs, adding further complexity to the process (Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, 2023)

Importantly, the origin of PG notably affects the leaching performance. PG derived from MPG generally exhibits higher REE recovery compared to PG derived from SPG. Bellefqih, Bilal and Mazouz (2024) demonstrated that using 2 M H₂SO₄ at a temperature 25C, with a leaching time of 2 hours and a L/S ratio of 8, PG derived from SPG, a recovery rate of up to 34% could be achieved, whereas the MPG derived PG yielded 85%, which is substantially higher. While these findings pertain specifically to REE, they underscore the broader importance of PF origin and mineralogical composition in determining leaching behaviour. For P recovery, similar principles may apply, though dedicated studies are required to confirm the extent of these effects.

2.3.4 Other valorisation routes for phosphogypsum

Due to PGs high Ca content, it has long been considered a viable substitute for natural gypsum in cement and gypsum plaster industries (Tayibi *et al.*, 2009). However, to ensure compatibility with industrial processes, PG must undergo several pretreatment steps. These include washing with water, washing in combination with neutralisation, thermal decomposition of impurities and lastly introducing additives that neutralise, mineralise, and regulate the crystallisation. In addition, PG must be dried and granulated, with a final moisture content below 12%, requiring mechanical steps such as grinding, sieving, and filtering (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

Among the various pretreatment options, thermal decomposition is particularly effective. Heat-treated PG has shown significantly reduced impurity content. For instance, treatment at 1000°C yields stable anhydrite, a phase suitable for construction use (Akin Altun and Sert, 2004). Besides construction use, the anhydrite can also be used to manufacture flooring tiles by mixing with catalysed monomers, glass fibres, pigments, and fly ash. This application requires grinding and sieving after the thermal process (Singh and Garg, 2000).

Beyond construction, PG has potential in agriculture due to its content of essential plant nutrients, such as Ca, S and P. One approach involves converting PG into a phosphate solution, followed by filtration and drying. The process is typically carried out in two steps: first by treating pre-calcined PG with alkaline carbonate reagent to pH 9-10, secondly by mixing the carbonate pulp with a semi-product of phosphoric acid production, washing with water to obtain a pH between 5-6. Another route uses ammonium carbonate solutions for conversion, though both methods face challenges related to process complexity and neutralisation demands (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

PG is also employed in soil reclamation, particularly for saline soils, by enhancing soil structure and calcium content. In composting, it can partially replace phosphorite flour, serving as a P-rich supplement (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

Additional recycling routes for PG include its use as a filler in coatings and paints, in the production of various salts, as an additive in asphalt, and as a component in road construction materials. These applications generally require minimal pretreatment and are especially viable in regions with high PG production and low regulatory constraints (Chernysh *et al.*, 2021).

3 Analytical methods

3.1 Molybdenum blue method quantified with UV-vis spectroscopy

The molybdenum blue (MB) method is a colorimetric analytical method for quantifying P in liquids. The method relies on the formation of a blue molybdenum complex which is formed in the presence of P. The reaction was first mentioned by C.W. Scheele in 1783. However, the discovery is credited to J.J. Berzelius for discovering MB ($\text{Mo}_5\text{O}_{14}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and being the first to determine the composition in 1826. That MB does not refer to a single species, but rather a collection of reduced molybdate compounds, was discovered in 1934 by Keggin, who proposed that the structures range of 12-heteropoly acids (Müller and Serain, 2000; Nagul *et al.*, 2015).

Furthermore, the MB method is a standard American Public Health Association (APHA) approved method for the detection of phosphate in drinking water, as well as fresh water. It can also be used for the quantification of arsenate in water. In the MB reaction, phosphate and arsenate react with a solution of molybdenum under acidic conditions. During the reaction, the Keggin structured heteropoly acid complexes, such as, 12-molybdophosphoric acid (12-MPA) (Eq. (8)) form. Secondly, a reduction of the heteropoly acid complexes occurs to form the blue-coloured phosphomolybdenum blue (PMB) (Eq. (9)). In Eq. (9), the reductant refers to the substance that donates electrons to another species, thereby reducing it while undergoing oxidation itself. In this case, the reductant transfers four electrons during the reaction. A common reductant for the MB method is ascorbic acid (Ibnul and Tripp, 2022).

There are several variations of the MB method; however, all require a strong acid, such as HNO_3 , HCl or H_2SO_4 . In this work, H_2SO_4 has been chosen as the acid used, due to

the PG already containing it. The method also requires a source of Mo (VI) and a reductant. The Keggin ions, 12-MPA composition $[X^{n+} Mo_{12}O_{40}]^{(8-n)-}$ forms due to orthophosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and other tetrahedral anions of the form XO_4 . To get the best colour intensity in the MB reaction for determining orthophosphates, the procedure should be carried out at pH 0-1. Furthermore, the concentration of acid, as well as the molybdate concentration determines the degree of protonation and thereby the determination of Mo (VI) speciation (Nagul *et al.*, 2015). The intensity of the blue colour correlates with the concentration of XO_4 species, such as orthophosphate, as illustrated in Figure 3. As the concentration increases, the blue colour intensifies accordingly. This intensity can be quantitatively measured using ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) spectroscopy.

Figure 3. P concentrations in standard solutions ranging from 1 ppm to 5 ppm and 10 ppm. As concentration increases, the intensity of the blue colour also increases, resulting from the reaction with the molybdenum blue reagent added to each solution.

UV-vis spectroscopy is a quantitative analytical technique. The approach is based on the interaction between matter and light, where the absorbance of near UV (180-390 nm) or visible (390-780 nm) radiation by a species in a solution is measured. The method is cost-effective, simple, versatile, and non-destructive as well as suitable for a large spectrum of organic compounds and some inorganic species. The technique is not commonly used for identification due to the limitation of varied species having similar spectrums, but for quantification of the amount of a known substance in a solution. The measured wavelength is inversely proportional to the amount of energy in the light. Consequently, shorter wavelengths have more energy than longer wavelengths (Khalid, Ishak and Chowdhury, 2024). The relationship between

absorbance and concentration is known as the Beer-Lambert law and is defined as Eq. (10). Where A is the absorbance of the solution, ϵ is the molar absorptivity ($\text{l mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$), L is the path length of radiation (cm), and c is the concentration (mol l^{-1}) and T stands for the transmittance, which describes how much light has passed through the sample (Worsfold, 2005).

$$A = \epsilon Lc = \log_{10} \left(\frac{I_0}{I} \right) = \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{T} \right) = -\log_{10}(T) \quad (10)$$

The absorbance can be obtained directly from the obtained spectrum, since it is related to the height of the absorbance peak, which can be typically found at a wavelength around 700-900 nm for the MB compound. The exact wavelength can vary slightly depending on the reaction conditions (Houck and Siegel, 2015). Generally, the concentration for both visible and UV light is directly proportional to the absorbance. A drawback with the method is that it is not accurate at high concentrations ($>0.01 \text{ mol l}^{-1}$), which is a result from interactions between analyte molecules (Worsfold, 2005).

The instrumentation for the spectroscopy consists of a radiation source, a sample compartment, a detector, and an output device. A tungsten filament is the most common source for visible radiation and a deuterium lamp is often used for near-UV radiation. As the wavelength-selection device a grating monochromator is typically used for the best resolution. The sample is placed in a cell, which is then placed in a compartment. The shape of the cuvette may vary based on the sample, but it typically has a square cross-section of 1 cm. The material of the cuvette is selected according to the wavelength range used in the analysis. Glass is suitable for wavelengths above 340 nm; plastic is common for visible light and quartz is preferred for both near-UV vis and visible light due to its broader transparency range. When choosing the cell, the sample should be taken into consideration to avoid reactions between sample and cell. The detector converts transmitted light into an electrical signal, with photomultiplier tubes being the most commonly used in the UV-vis spectroscopy due to their sensitivity and efficiency (Worsfold, 2005). A simplified schematic of the working principle of the UV-vis spectroscopy is shown in Figure 4. The spectrophotometer can either have a single- or double beam configuration. The main difference between the

two is that the single-beam instrument is cheaper, whereas the double-beam instrument is more optimal for spectral scanning (Worsfold, 2005).

Strengths associated with the technique include that it is non-destructive, quick and easy to use, requiring minimal processing, as well as inexpensive. Weaknesses include possible interference from multiple absorbing species and light scattering due to possible presence of bubbles in the cuvette, which results in irreproducible results (Justin, 2023).

Figure 4. Simplified schematic of the working principle of the UV-vis spectroscopy, adapted from Worsfold, (2005).

3.2 Complexometric titration with EDTA

Complexometric titration is an analytical technique used for determining the concentration of metal ions in a solution. The method relies on the formation of stable, water-soluble complexes between metal ions and a complexing agent. Several complexing agents can be used depending on the specific metal ion being analysed, including cyanide, fluoride and most commonly ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, called EDTA (Kozak and Townshend, 2019).

EDTA (H_4Y) forms stable complexes with most metals. In aqueous solutions, EDTA typically exists in its deprotonated form, Y^{4-} , which forms strong 1:1 stoichiometric complex with most metal ions. The only notable exceptions are alkali metals, which form complexes too weak to be analysed. The general reaction between a metal ion (Me^{n+}) and EDTA is shown in Eq. (11) (Kozak and Townshend, 2019).

The stability of the resulting complex can be quantified by the stability constant K_{MeY} , which is the equilibrium constant for the reaction above (Eq. (12)). A higher value of K_{MeY} indicates a more stable complex (Kozak and Townshend, 2019).

$$K_{MeY} = \frac{[MeY^{(4-n)-}]}{[Me^{n+}][Y^{4-}]} \quad (12)$$

The formation of metal-EDTA complexes is pH-dependent. Stronger complexes can form at lower pH values, while weaker complexes require higher pH to prevent protonation of the complexing agent. Additionally, the complexation reaction releases protons, which can alter the pH of the solution. To maintain a stable pH during titration, a suitable buffer is added to the sample solution. (Kozak and Townshend, 2019).

To visually detect the endpoint of the titration, metal ion indicators are used. These can typically be organic dyes that form a weakly coloured complex with the metal ions. As EDTA is added, it displaces the indicator from the metal ion due to the formation of a more stable complex. This results in a distinct colour change, signalling the endpoint of the titration (Kozak and Townshend, 2019).

In this thesis, Eriochrome black T (EBT) is used as the indicator. The indicator behaves as an acid/base indicator and as a metal ion indicator. For the determination of calcium ions, the optimal pH is approximately 10. Which can be maintained using an ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer (Malmstadt and Hadjiioannou, 1958).

The advantage with the colorimetric titrations is its high selectivity for metal ions and wide applicability. The method is also non-destructive and accessible due to inexpensive reagents and simple equipment. Drawbacks of the method include pH sensitivity, possible interference from other ions and limitations with the indicator depending on which metal ions are being analysed (Kozak and Townshend, 2019).

3.3 ICP-OES

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) is a modern and multifunctional analytical technique used for the elemental analysis of a wide range of sample types, including environmental, industrial, plant, tissue, and pharmaceutical materials. The method is suitable for detecting elements across various concentration levels (Measurlabs, no date). ICP-OES offers rapid, multi-elemental analysis with minimal interference and sensitivity ranging from parts per billion (ppb) to parts per million (ppm) for most elements. It is applicable to liquids, solids and gases (Khan *et al.*, 2022).

The technique operates by exciting atoms and ions by using a high-temperature plasma generated by radio-frequency discharge. This excitation causes the particles to emit photons, which are detected and analysed to determine elemental composition. Solid samples must be converted into a liquid form, either through extraction or acid digestion. Gaseous samples are introduced into the ICP torch via an auxiliary carrier gas stream. Liquid samples are pumped into a nebulizer (Fig. 6), which converts them into an aerosol or mist. The aerosol is then transported via a spray chamber to the ICP torch (Khan *et al.*, 2022).

The ICP torch is composed of concentric glass tubes through which argon gas flows. The innermost tube carries the sample, while the outer and intermediate tube carry argon gas that help maintain the plasma temperature between 8000 and 10,000 K (Corns *et al.*, 1993). Within the plasma, sample molecules are atomized and ionized and then excited by the elevated temperature. As the excited electrons return to lower energy levels, photons are emitted. These photons are collected by a concave mirror and directed toward a wavelength selection device, such as a monochromator or prism, which separates the emission wavelengths. A photodetector then converts the separated light into electrical signals (Khan *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 5. Simplified scheme of the instrumentation of ICP-OES, adapted from Khan *et al.*, (2022)

Advantages with this method include that it is a versatile, sensitive technique with low detection limits, fewer chemical interferences, and is less time-consuming compared to other spectrometric techniques. The method allows for simultaneous multi-elemental analysis, has a wide dynamic range, facilitating accurate quantification of elements in varying concentrations within a single run. Disadvantages include higher detection limits compared to ICP-MS, sample destruction, eliminating the possibility of sample recovery post-analysis, as well as background emissions, which can interfere with the detection of analyte signals, possibly affecting the accuracy of the analysis (Khan *et al.*, 2022; Lab, 2024a).

3.4 SEM-EDS

Scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) is an analytical technique used for the examination, analysis, and characterisation of microstructural morphology and the chemical composition of materials (Zhou *et al.*, 2007). Its primary function is to magnify small features and objects that are otherwise invisible to the human eye. A SEM-EDS system can magnify objects up to one million times their original size and resolve features smaller than 1 nm (Ul-Hamid, 2018).

The instrument operates by directing a beam of electrons, typically in the range of 100 to 30,000 electron volts, onto the material using an electron gun (Fig. 5). The initial spot size produced by the gun is too large to produce a sharp image; therefore, the SEM-EDS is equipped with electromagnetic lenses to compress the electron beam and focus it onto the sample. The electrons emitted from the sample are then collected and detected by an electron detector. Both secondary electrons (SE) and backscattered electrons (BSE) are used to generate images that reveal topographic and compositional contrast. The resulting signals are processed via a computer control system, allowing adjustments to brightness and contrast to optimise image clarity. The SEs are low-energy electrons emitted from the surface, created by interactions between the electron beam and sample atoms, which are primarily used for surface visualisation and topographical imaging. In contrast, BSEs are high-energy electrons reflected from deeper within the sample, resulting from elastic collisions with atomic nuclei, making them suitable for distinguishing differences in elemental composition. Therefore, BSEs are associated with EDS (Ul-Hamid, 2018).

In addition to secondary and backscattered electron emissions, X-rays are produced when the electron beam penetrates and interacts with the subsurface volume of the sample. These X-rays enable elemental analysis (Mohammed and Abdullah, 2018), offering insight into properties such as composition, morphology, grain size and shape, and grain boundaries (Ul-Hamid, 2018). The detection limit typically ranges from 0.1 to 0.5 wt%, depending on the element, matrix, and operating conditions. For the elements analysed in this study, this range applies (Zhou *et al.*, 2007; Bale *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of SEM-EDS-EDS adapted from Lab, (2024b).

There are several advantages to using SEM-EDS. A wide variety of specimens can be examined with minimal to no sample preparation, allowing for rapid and convenient analysis. Depending on the apparatus setup, the technique is suitable for both wet and dry samples, and it is relatively cost-effective and more accessible compared to alternative analytical methods (Ul-Hamid, 2018).

However, the method also has limitations. These include restrictions on sample size, applicability only to solid specimens, and the inability of SEM-EDS to detect light elements such as hydrogen (H), helium (He), and lithium (Li) (Ul-Hamid, 2018).

4 Experimental section

4.1 Materials

The experiments were conducted using PG obtained from two distinct sources, both of which were from their landfills. The first originates from Finland and is referred to as FG. The second PG was sourced from Kutina, Croatia, and is referred to as CrG. The gypsums originate from the company's phosphoric acid production (Bituh *et al.*, 2021). The phosphate rock used in the production of these PGs comes from different geological origins. The CrG was primarily derived from sedimentary rock imported from Morocco, whereas FG was produced using phosphate rock of magmatic origin (Mononen *et al.*, 2013; Bituh *et al.*, 2021).

Common acids and bases were selected as solvents for the leaching experiments. For each solvent, four L/S ratios were chosen: 100, 50, 20, and 10 (ml/g). These solvents used were 0.1 M and 1 M solutions of H₂SO₄, HCl, and CA, as well as 1 M NH₃ and NH₄Cl. NH₃ and NH₄Cl were only tested at 1 M concentration, as experiments showed that 1 M solvents were generally more effective than their 0.1 M counterparts. To keep the experimental scope manageable, these two solvents were therefore only evaluated at the higher concentration. Ultrapure water (18.2 MΩ·cm) was used as a baseline reference. All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade: 25% NH₃ manufactured by J.T. Baker, 37% HCl manufactured by Supelco, 96% H₂SO₄ by Sigma-Aldrich, NH₄Cl by VWR Chemicals, and CA by VWR Chemicals.

4.2 Leaching experiments

For each experiment, 5 g of pre-dried PG was added to the liquid phase. Drying was performed at 110°C overnight in a Memmert drying cupboard. The drying step was essential for sample preparation, as it ensured the removal of the free water content. Drying at this relatively high temperature caused all dihydrates present to convert into hemihydrate, leaving a well-defined sample. Leaching was carried out in a Stuart SSL1 orbital shaker, which provided smooth shaking with an orbit of 16mm at a speed of

200 rpm. This shaker was selected for its compatibility with various vessel sizes and its suitability for the experimental setup.

The leaching experiments were primarily conducted at room temperature, i.e., 22°C, unless stated otherwise. After each experiment, the resulting slurry was filtered using Whatman Grade 41 and Grade 42 ashless filter papers with a diameter of 90mm. The particle retention is 20-25 µm for the grade 41 filter papers and 2.5 µm for the grade 42 filter paper. The filters were chosen for their compatibility with the experimental procedure.

Table 4 shows an overview of the prepared samples for the leaching experiments performed at room temperature.

Table 4. List of prepared samples for leaching experiments performed at room temperature.

Sample name (Finnish gypsum)	Sample name (Croatian gypsum)	Solvent	L/S ratio (ml/g)
FG1	CrG1	H ₂ O	100
FG2	CrG2	H ₂ O	50
FG3	CrG3	H ₂ O	20
FG4	CrG4	H ₂ O	10
FG9	CrG5	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	100
FG10	CrG6	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	50
FG11	CrG7	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	20
FG12	CrG8	1 M H ₂ SO ₄	10
FG5	CrG9	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	100
FG6	CrG10	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	50
FG7	CrG11	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	20
FG8	CrG12	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	10
FG21	CrG21	1 M NH ₃	100
FG22	CrG22	1 M NH ₃	50
FG23	CrG23	1 M NH ₃	20
FG24	CrG24	1 M NH ₃	10
FG13	CrG13	1 M CA	100
FG14	CrG14	1 M CA	50
FG15	CrG15	1 M CA	20
FG16	CrG16	1 M CA	10
FG17	CrG17	0.1 M CA	100
FG18	CrG18	0.1 M CA	50
FG19	CrG19	0.1 M CA	20
FG20	CrG20	0.1 M CA	10
FG25	CrG25	0.1 M HCl	100
FG26	CrG26	0.1 M HCl	50
FG27	CrG27	0.1 M HCl	20
FG28	CrG28	0.1 M HCl	10
FG29	CrG29	1 M HCl	100
FG30	CrG30	1 M HCl	50
FG31	CrG31	1 M HCl	20
FG32	CrG32	1 M HCl	10
FG33	CrG33	1 M NH ₄ Cl	100
FG34	CrG34	1 M NH ₄ Cl	50
FG35	CrG35	1 M NH ₄ Cl	20
FG36	CrG36	1 M NH ₄ Cl	10

4.2.1 Influence of leaching time

The evolution of pH and electrical conductivity was continuously monitored during the leaching of FG samples with water (samples FG1, FG2, FG3, and FG4), using a WTWs pH/Cond 3320 multi-parameter meter. This real-time monitoring was essential for determining the optimum leaching time, particularly in relation to the solubility and speciation of the target elements. The chosen leaching time was 2 hours.

4.2.2 Influence of leaching temperature

To investigate the effect of temperature on the leaching efficiency, a series of experiments using CrG was performed using a fixed L/S ratio of 100 ml/g and 1 M HCl as the leaching solvent at varying temperatures of 30°C, 50°C, and 70°C.

4.2.3 Reproducibility of experiments

To assess the reproducibility of the results, replicate experiments were conducted using 0.1 M H₂SO₄ as the solvent and performed in triplicate for L/S ratios 100, 50, 20, and 10 ml/g.

4.3 Analysis methods

4.3.1 Raw material characterisation methods

The particle size distribution of the studied PGs was determined using a laser particle size analyser (Malvern Mastersizer Hydro). Analyses were carried out by Evelina Koivisto, Laboratory of Process Design and Systems Engineering at ÅAU. A sample density of 1 g/cm³ was used for setting the software, and the sample was prepared by being mixed with a saturated solution of synthetic gypsum to prevent the raw material from dissolving in the solution, obtaining a more accurate measurement.

The composition of raw solid materials was analysed at a commercial laboratory, situated in Sweden, using inductively coupled plasma-sector field mass spectroscopy

(ICP-SFMS). The moisture content of the PGs as received from the landfill site was determined by performing a set of experiments in triplicate at 110°C. Accurate determination of the moisture content enabled quantification of the amount of PG dissolved during the leaching experiments. The composition of the dried raw material was determined with SEM-EDS from four overall analyses.

Gamma spectrometry was conducted to assess the radiological safety of the raw materials. The radiological analyses were conducted in the department of physics at ÅAU. The materials were analysed as received, and the technique allowed for the determination of ^{226}Ra content in Bq per gram.

4.3.2 UV-Vis spectroscopy in combination with the MB method for P analysis

The analysis of P was conducted following a DGT research method for colorimetric analysis of P using molybdenum blue (DGT Research, no date). The reagent used for the technique consisted of 2.5 M H_2SO_4 , 40 g/l ammonium molybdate ($(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}$), 2.8 g/l potassium antimonyltartrate ($\text{K}_2\text{Sb}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_2\text{O}_6)_2$), and ascorbic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$), of which 1.76 g was dissolved in 100 ml of ultrapure water. A reagent solution of 20 ml was prepared by combining 10 ml of the prepared 2.5 M H_2SO_4 , 3 ml of the ammonium molybdate solution, 1 ml of the prepared potassium antimonyltartrate solution, and 6 ml of the prepared ascorbic acid. For each sample analysed, 1 ml of the mixed reagent was added to 5 ml of the sample. Due to the lower accuracy of samples with concentrations above 0.01 mol/l, many samples required dilution prior to analysis, which was determined by comparing the blue colour of the sample to the prepared standard solutions. The dilution ratios used are listed in Appendix C.

The absorbance and concentration in the UV-visible range (190-900 nm) were measured using the Shimadzu UV2501 PC UV Spectrometer. Standards solutions were prepared using potassium phosphate (K_3PO_4) to create a 100 ppm phosphate stock solution, which was then diluted to obtain concentrations between 1 ppm and 5 ppm. These concentrations were selected to ensure clear visibility of the characteristic peak at 710 nm, which loses its distinctiveness at higher concentrations due to absorbance saturation.

Figure 7. UV-vis spectra presented as absorbance as a function of wavelength of standard solutions containing P in concentrations from 1 to 5

To quantify the amount of P in the samples, the resulting spectrogram from the UV-vis measurement for the standard solutions was analysed (Fig. 7). A calibration line was generated by plotting the absorbance at the characteristic peak against the concentration (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Calibration line constructed for the determination of P in the leachates, showing the absorbance at $\lambda=710$ nm as a function of the concentration of the standard solutions

Based on the linear equation from the calibration line (Fig. 8), the concentration of P in each sample was calculated as:

$$C_{after\ MB\ dilution} = \frac{Absorbance - b}{a}$$

Where the absorbance is the measured value from the UV-vis spectrometer, and a and b are the slope and intercept from the calibration line:

$$y = ax + b$$

The concentration before dilution (mg/l) was calculated as:

$$C_{before\ dilution} = C_{after\ MB\ dilution} \cdot dilution\ factor$$

Subsequently, the concentration of P (mmol/l) is calculated as:

$$C_P = \frac{C_{before\ dilution}}{M_P}, \text{ where } M_P = 30.97\ \text{g/mol}$$

The recovered amount of P (%) was calculated as:

$$Recovered\ amount\ of\ P\ (\%) = \left(\frac{V_{sample} \cdot Conc_{before\ dilution}}{m_{sample} \cdot C_{YG}} \right) \cdot 100$$

4.3.3 Complexometric titration with EDTA for Ca analysis

A complexometric titration with EDTA was performed to quantify the concentration of Ca^{2+} in the liquid samples. To maintain a stable pH of 10 during the titration, an ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer (NH_3-NH_4Cl) was used. The buffer was prepared by dissolving 34 g of NH_4Cl in 200 ml of H_2O , then adding 285 ml of NH_3 and diluting until the volume reached 500 ml. Prior to titration, the samples were diluted with H_2O to ensure that the Ca^{2+} concentration remained below 200 mg/l. This dilution was necessary because the optimal range for EDTA titration lies below this concentration.

The titration was carried out using a 0.05 M EDTA solution as the titrant, along with Eriochrome black T as the indicator. Each sample was titrated in triplicate to ensure accuracy and reproducibility of the results.

Since EDTA forms a 1:1 complex with Ca^{2+} :

$$\text{mol Ca}^{2+} = \text{mol EDTA} = M_{\text{EDTA}} \cdot V_{\text{EDTA}}$$

The concentration of Ca^{2+} in the liquid samples varies based on the L/S ratio. For a L/S ratio of 50 ml/g, the total volume of the liquid was 0.25 l, and thus the Ca^{2+} concentration could be calculated as:

$$[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{g/l}} = [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{mol/l}} \cdot M_{\text{Ca}} = [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{mol/l}} \cdot 40.078 \text{ g/mol}$$

The percentage of dissolved Ca^{2+} in the sample was then calculated as:

$$\% \text{Ca}_{\text{dissolved}}^{2+} = \frac{[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{g}} \cdot V_{\text{sample}}}{m_{\text{total Ca amount in sample}}} \cdot 100$$

From these values, the average dissolved Ca^{2+} content was determined.

4.3.4 ICP-OES for liquid elemental analysis

Elemental analysis of liquid samples was performed using ICP-OES, with measurements carried out on a PerkinElmer Optima 5300 DV spectrometer. To ensure accurate quantification and avoid exceeding the detection limits of the instrument, the samples were diluted prior to analysis. S and Ca samples were diluted 100-fold, while P samples were diluted 5-fold with 0.1 M HNO_3 for all samples except for the NH_3 samples, which were diluted with 1 M HCl . These dilution ratios were selected based on preliminary tests and expected concentration ranges from the developed MB compounds in the leachates.

4.3.5 SEM-EDS for solid sample characterisation

SEM-EDS, based on BSE, was employed to analyse the structural and elemental composition of both the raw material and the solid residues. The analyses were conducted using a Leo Gemini 1530 electron microscope, equipped with a Thermo Scientific UltraDry Silicon Drift Detector, operated at high vacuum conditions. This

setup enabled high-resolution imaging and precise elemental mapping, providing detailed insights into the surface morphology and chemical composition of the solid samples. Prior to analysis, the dried samples were mounted on carbon tape to improve the conductivity of the sample and thereby enhancing image quality. Overview imaging was performed at 30x and 100x magnifications to assess general morphology, while elemental mapping and point analyses were conducted at 500x magnification. The morphological analysis of the solid residues was conducted to gain insight into the structural and compositional changes occurring during leaching. Understanding these changes helps to explain the efficiency and selectivity of different solvents, particularly in terms of phase dissolution, precipitation, or reformation.

SEM-EDS was selected over ICP-SFMS for solid phase analysis due to its cost-effectiveness, in-house availability, and its ability to provide sufficiently accurate elemental data for the scope of this study. Additionally, ICP-SFMS was associated with relatively high variations in concentrations of $\pm 30\%$. SEM-EDS offer more consistent results, with lower variability, making it a more suitable choice for this study.

4.4 Generative artificial intelligence

Generative artificial intelligence tools were used to support the writing process of this thesis. Specifically, Microsoft Copilot (Microsoft, 2023) was employed with grammar verification and synonym suggestions.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Raw material characterisation

The CrG is a beige-coloured material, while FG appears white. Both materials are wet and powdery and contain agglomerates. The CrG exhibit a higher level of impurities, including small rocks from the disposal site, as well as organic contaminants such as feathers and avian feces.

The morphology of the PG samples was examined with SEM-EDS images. Figure 9 presents the images of FG, while Figure 10 shows the CrG images, both at magnifications of 100x and 500x. The morphological differences between the two raw materials are minimal and can be considered negligible for the purpose of this study. At 100x magnification, the particles appear irregular in shape and size. The scale bar of 200 μm indicates that most particles fall within the 50-300 μm range, consistent with the particle size distribution data. At 500x magnification, finer surface features are visible. The particles have a rough texture, which may enhance surface area and may affect leaching kinetics. Overall, the morphological differences between FG and CrG are minimal.

Figure 9. SEM-EDS images of FG taken at different magnifications: 100x (left) and 500x (right), showing the morphology of FG.

Figure 10. SEM-EDS images of CrG taken at different magnifications: 100x (left) and 500x (right), showing the morphology of CrG.

As shown in Figure 11, the particle size ranges from 1 to 800 μm , with the majority of the particles clustered around 100 μm for both FG and CrG. This relatively fine particle size suggests good dispersion potential in aqueous media, which can influence leaching kinetics.

Figure 11. Particle size distribution of FG and CrG. PG was added as a solid to a saturated $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution.

Table 5 presents the elemental content of both untreated and dried raw materials. Drying at 110°C significantly increased the measured values of P, Al, and Si in both CrG and FG samples. This increase reflects the reduction in moisture content, which concentrates the elements in the remaining solid mass. Notably the Ca content remained stable in CrG but increased in FG upon drying, while S content increased in CrG and remained unchanged in FG. These differences suggest slight compositional

variations between the PG matrices of the two raw materials. Nonetheless, the composition of the dried PGs is overall similar. However, these minor compositional differences may influence leaching behaviour, particularly in acid leaching processes where Ca solubility affects acid consumption, pH buffering and the formation of secondary precipitates (Wang *et al.*, 2018).

Table 5 also presents the moisture content of the raw material. Standards deviations (STD) was calculated based on the differences in the results from the experiments. FG exhibits slightly higher moisture content than CrG, which can reflect the difference in origin and storage conditions. While the difference is relatively minor, it is relevant for quantifying the actual amount of solid PG dissolved during leaching experiments.

Table 5. Composition of the studied PG raw materials presented in weight percent (wt%). Composition of the untreated raw materials were analysed with ICP-SFMS and samples dried overnight at 110°C were analysed with SEM-EDS at 30x and 100x magnification. The table also includes the average free water content (%) for the untreated raw material, determined by mass loss after drying at 110°C.

	Ca	S	P	Al	Si	Moisture content (%)
CrG	27.00 ±	14.00 ±	0.15 ±	0.06 ±	0.09 ±	23.87 ±
untreated	8.01	4.20	0.05	0.02	0.03	3.98
FG	25.00 ±	22.00 ±	0.20 ±	0.02 ±	0.02 ±	29.17 ±
untreated	7.50	6.60	0.06	0.01	0.01	3.32
CrG 110°C	27.07 ±	21.18 ±	0.35 ±	0.22 ±	0.25 ±	
	1.25	0.84	0.08	0.03	0.05	
FG 110°C	27.88 ±	21.21 ±	0.31 ±	0.17 ±	0.32 ±	
	1.57	0.90	0.30	0.03	0.04	

The composition of FG can be compared to the results reported by Mattila and Zevenhoven, (2015), who analysed FG using ICP-MS. Their findings are mostly consistent with the current study, except for a deviation in the reported Ca content, which they reported to be 90 wt%. This is significantly higher than the 25-28 wt% observed in this study. This discrepancy is likely due to differences in data presentation, as their values may include Ca bound in gypsum compounds (e.g., $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The composition of CrG can be compared to PG samples characterised by (Akfas *et al.*, 2023), who analysed Moroccan PG using ICP-OES and ICP-MS.

They reported Ca content of approximately 23 wt%, S content of around 18 wt%, and Si content of approximately 0.80 wt%. These are all values comparable to those observed for CrG, even though the Si content is slightly higher. Nonetheless, the overall similarity in major element composition supports the reliability of the analytical methods used in this study.

The CrG exhibited ^{226}Ra levels of 0.41 ± 0.02 Bq/g, indicating that it is safe to handle under standard laboratory conditions. The FG sample showed levels below the detection limit of 0.006 Bq/g, indicating no radiological concern. Based on these findings, both PG types are presumed to fall below the regulatory threshold for restricted handling and do not pose a health risk when handled correctly.

5.2 Experimental conditions and method validation

5.2.1 Influence of time on leaching efficiency

Figure 12 shows the change of pH as a function of time during the leaching experiment of FG with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 . At the lower L/S ratios, the pH reached a constant level within a few minutes. However, for the higher L/S ratios, it took more than 30 minutes to reach a stable pH level. To ensure that the systems are close to equilibrium when analysed, a duration of 2 hours was chosen for the leaching experiments. This extended time also accounts for the potential slow release of less readily soluble elements, such as REEs, which may not significantly influence the bulk pH but can continue to dissolve over more extended periods of time. Sufficient contact time is therefore essential to ensure the full leaching behaviour is captured for both major and trace elements.

Figure 12. Changes in pH for leaching experiments of FG with water as solvent at L/S ratios 100, 50, 20 and 10 ml/g (FG1-FG4). The pH stabilises within 5 minutes in two cases, suggesting that in that time, the most reactive phases have been dissolved.

5.2.2 Influence of temperature on leaching efficiency

Figure 13 presents the results from the leaching experiments at elevated temperatures (30, 50 and 70°C). The figure presents the recovery of P as a function of temperature. The recovery trends differ slightly between the two PG types. CrG samples exhibit a clear positive correlation between temperature and P recovery. Recovery increases from approximately 60% at 30°C to around 85% at 70°C, indicating that elevated temperatures enhance the leaching efficiency for this material. FG samples show a more complex trend and a more moderate increase in recovery with increasing temperature. Recovery begins at approximately 55% at 30°C, rises sharply to about 75% at 50°C, but then slightly decreases to 70% at 70°C. This deviation suggests that the 50°C data point may be anomalous. Overall, these findings align with the theory mentioned in Section 2.3.1, that higher temperatures can enhance leaching by increasing reaction kinetics and solubility of phosphate species. The improvement in, P recovery at moderate temperatures (e.g. 50 °C) compared to lower temperatures (e.g. 20 °C – 35 %), suggests that operating at intermediate temperatures may offer an optimal balance between efficiency and energy input. This observation is consistent with previous studies by (Mashifana, Ntuli and Okonta, 2019) and Dong *et al.*, 2025), who reported similar benefits of moderate heating. Nevertheless, further research is needed to evaluate the effect of elevated temperatures on the recovery efficiency and to validate these assumptions.

Figure 13. Recovered amount of P (%) as a function of temperature (°C) for samples leached with 1M HCl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g.

5.2.3 Reproducibility of the experimental procedure

To investigate the reproducibility of the leaching experiments, leaching of FG with 0.1 M H₂SO₄ was performed in triplicate. Figure 14 displays the results as the amount of dissolved P as a function of L/S ratios. As shown, the deviations between replicates are relatively large. One reason for these deviations can be errors in the analysis method. On the other hand, the calibration line from the UV-Vis measurements indicates good accuracy, and therefore, the deviations are likely caused by the inhomogeneity of the samples. General trends can be observed between the samples. For example, higher amounts of P dissolve at higher L/S ratios. This statement is consistent with literature, as the L/S ratio generally is considered a key factor in leaching experiments (Richardson, J.F.; Harker, J.H.; Backhurst, J.R., 2002). A trend line was included in the figure solely as a visual aid. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.9252$) was calculated based on the mean values of the triplicates and reflects a strong correlation between L/S ratio and the percentage of P dissolved.

Figure 14. Dissolved amount of P (%) as a function of L/S ratio (ml/g) for FG leached with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 . Experiments were carried out in triplicate to ensure reproducibility of the experimental setup. A trend line is included for visual guidance. The error bars represent STDs.

5.3 Comparison of the leaching behaviour of FG and CrG

5.3.1 Mass loss behaviour

The mass loss observed during leaching serves as an indicator of the solubility and reactivity of the PG during the different conditions. For each solvent, the effect of the L/S ratio was evaluated by measuring the corresponding percentage of mass loss. The figures presented in the following section were derived from the initial and final sample weights after leaching. Trend lines were added to aid visual interpretation and do not imply a correlation between the mass loss and L/S ratio. The complete calculation data for each sample is provided in Appendix A.

Figure 15 presents the mass loss for CrG and FG samples subjected to leaching with 0.1 M solutions of HCl, H_2SO_4 , CA, and H_2O . A general increase in mass loss was observed with increasing L/S ratio for all tested solvents, indicating enhanced dissolution of PG as the solvent volume increased. Among the tested 0.1 M solvents, HCl demonstrated the highest leaching efficiency for both PG types. At an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, approximately 65% of the sample mass was dissolved, significantly surpassing the performance of the other solvents. CA, H_2SO_4 , and H_2O leached samples exhibited comparable mass loss behaviour, with substantially lower mass loss

values compared to HCl. The resulting mass loss for them was approximately 30% at the highest L/S ratio.

When comparing the mass loss percentages of these FG and CrG samples, the overall trends regarding solvent type and L/S ratio are similar. In both cases does a higher L/S ratio corresponds to increased mass loss, and the relative performance of the solvents follows a comparable pattern.

Figure 15. Mass loss (%) of CrG and FG samples leached with 0.1 M HCl, H₂SO₄, CA, and deionized water as a function of L/S ratio (ml/g)

Figure 16 illustrates the mass loss behaviour of CrG and FG samples leached with 1 M solutions of H₂SO₄, HCl, CA, NH₃, NH₄Cl, and H₂O. As with the 0.1 M experiments, a consistent increase in mass loss was observed with increasing L/S ratio, reaffirming the influence of solvent volume on the leaching performance. This trend suggests that higher liquid availability facilitates higher mass transport and solubility of PG components, regardless of solvent type.

Among the tested 1 M solvents, HCl exhibited the highest mass loss percentage. At an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, the CrG sample showed a mass loss of approximately 95%. NH₄Cl also resulted in substantial mass loss, slightly exceeding 80%. In contrast, 1 M solutions of H₂SO₄ and CA produced higher mass losses compared to their 0.1 M counterparts but remained significantly lower than those of 1M HCl and NH₄Cl,

ranging between 20% and 30%. This difference highlights the role of proton availability in promoting solubility efficiency.

A similar trend was observed for FG samples. The highest dissolution was achieved with 1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, resulting in nearly complete dissolution (~100% mass loss). 1 M NH₄Cl followed by a mass loss of around 85%. The other solvents showed notably lower efficiencies, with mass loss values ranging from 30% to 40%.

As shown in Figure 16, no mass loss data is available for the samples leached with 1 M CA at L/S ratios of 10 and 20 ml/g, due to an observed increase in sample weight post-leaching. This anomaly may be attributed to the formation of complex compounds or precipitation reactions between CA and components of the PG matrix.

Figure 16. Mass loss (%) of CrG and FG samples leached with 1 M HCl, H₂SO₄, CA, NH₃, NH₄ water as a function of L/S ratio (ml/g)

As PG mainly consists of CaSO₄, a high mass loss is correlated with a high dissolution of Ca. CaSO₄ has a solubility of approximately 2.5 g/l at room temperature in H₂O. With an L/S ratio of 100, this corresponds to a solubility of 10 g/l or roughly 25% of the solid mass. When comparing this with the dissolution of both FG and CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 in H₂O, the mass loss was approximately 25 %, which aligns with the known solubility of CaSO₄ (Klimchouk, 1996), indicating good experimental

accuracy. The solubility of CaSO_4 is also the reasoning to why the higher L/S ratio is more effective in breaking down the PG matrix and solubilising its components compared to lower L/S ratios.

Under the tested conditions, mass loss for PG was comparable between samples leached with H_2O and H_2SO_4 , suggesting that solution acidity has a limited influence on the mass loss. Among the investigated solvents, 1 M HCl consistently resulted in the highest mass loss. NH_4Cl also proved effective at dissolving PG samples. The enhanced dissolution observed in HCl and NH_4Cl can be attributed to the chloride compound in them. Chloride ions promote the formation of soluble calcium chloride species, which reduce the activity of free Ca^{2+} ions and shift the dissolution equilibrium of CaSO_4 toward further dissolution. In acidic media, the partial protonation of SO_4 and HSO_4^- further reduces sulphate ion concentration, enhancing solubility. Although NH_4Cl is not acidic, it contributes through ionic strength and chloride availability, facilitating dissolution (Zhang *et al.*, 2013; Jebali *et al.*, 2024).

5.3.2 Recovery of P

This section presents the results for P recovery from the PG samples. As outlined in the experimental section, recovery was calculated based on the mass of P detected in the liquid phase after leaching, relative to the initial concentration of P in the solid sample. The figure illustrates the percentage of P recovered as a function of the L/S ratio in mg/l. Logarithmic trend lines were fitted to each dataset to aid visual interpretation and are intended solely as a visual aid and do not imply a statistical correlation between L/S ratio and recovery. The full dataset to generate the figure is available in Appendix B.

Figure 17 shows the recovery of P for both CrG and FG samples. The solvents NH_3 , NH_4Cl , and CA were excluded from the figure, as they did not yield detectable amounts of P when analysed using UV-vis in combination with the MB method. This indicates either that P recovery was below the detection limit, i.e., no blue colour was developed with the MB method, or that complex formation with the reagent interfered with the analytical method.

For the FG samples, the results indicate that higher acid concentrations lead to improved leaching efficiency. The highest recovery, approximately 95% was achieved using 1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g. This performance exceeded that of 1 M H₂SO₄, which reached a recovery of around 80%. Across all extractants, an increase in the L/S ratio tended to enhance P recovery, although the rate of improvement diminished at higher ratios, suggesting a plateau in extraction efficiency. H₂O resulted in the lowest recovery rate, approximately 20% for both PG types, highlighting the necessity of acid-based solvents for effective P extraction. While H₂SO₄ was capable of dissolving P, it generally underperformed compared to HCl. According to Shah *et al.*, (2022) and Dong *et al.*, (2025) this may be attributed to the tendency of sulphate media to promote gypsum reformation, which can limit P recovery. Nonetheless, the recovery rates obtained with H₂SO₄ seem to follow similar trends as other studies, e.g. Shah *et al.*, (2022) reported a recovery of around 60% when leached with a 4% H₂SO₄.

The CrG samples did not show a consistent trend of improved recovery with higher acid concentrations. For HCl, both 1 M and 0.1 M solutions yielded comparable results, with the 0.1 M solution slightly outperforming the 1 M solution at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g (76% vs. 70%). A similar pattern was observed for H₂SO₄, where the 0.1 M solution achieved a recovery of 55%, compared to 40% for the 1 M solution. Similar to the FG samples, the HCl outperformed the other solvents, as mentioned in Section 5.3.1. This may be attributed to the formation of chloride complexes, which facilitates the dissolution of Ca while P remains in less soluble forms.

Figure 17. P recovery (%) from CrG and FG samples as a function of L/S ratio (ml/g), based on UV-vis and SEM-EDS data. Crosses represent extraction using 1 M solvent solutions, while dot indicate 0.1 M concentrations. NH_3 , NH_4Cl and CA are excluded due to undetectable P levels in UV-vis analysis. NH_3 , NH_4Cl and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$ are excluded due to undetectable P levels in UV-vis analysis.

5.3.3 Recovery of Ca

The figures in this subsection were generated by quantifying the amount of Ca recovered from the leaching experiments. This was achieved by analysing the remaining liquids using ICP-OES and the solid residues using SEM-EDS. The accuracy of the ICP-OES analysis was verified through EDTA titrations; a comparison between the methods is available in Section 5.6.

The following figures illustrate the recovery of Ca (%) as a function of the L/S ratio (ml/g). Only data corresponding to L/S ratios of 100 and 50 ml/g were analysed with ICP-OES, due to time constraints, cost considerations, and the fact that these ratios showed the most promising results based on the mass loss and the recovery of P. To aid in the interpretation of the results, linear trend lines were fitted to each dataset. These trend lines are intended solely as a visual aid and do not imply a statistical correlation between the Ca recovery and L/S ratio. The complete datasets and corresponding calculations are provided in Appendix C.

Figure 18 presents the Ca recovery for CrG and FG samples leached with 0.1 M solvents. Consistent with the trends observed in the P recovery, an increase in the L/S

ratio generally led to a higher Ca recovery. Among the tested solvents, HCl demonstrated the highest efficiency, yielding significantly greater recovery percentages compared to the other extractants. Both PG types exhibited comparable trends. The largest variation in Ca recovery was observed with leaching using 0.1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, which resulted in approximately 70% Ca recovery for CrG and 60% for FG.

Figure 18. Ca recovery (%) from CrG and FG samples, leached with 0.1 M solvents as a function of L/S ratio (ml/g), based on ICP-OES and SEM-EDS data

Figure 19 presents the Ca recovery for CrG and FG samples leached with 1 M solvents. The results highlight two solvents that were notably more effective than others: HCl, which yielded recovery rates exceeding 100%, and NH₄Cl, which achieved a recovery rate of approximately 90% for the CrG sample and around 100% for the FG sample, at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g.

The recovery rate for HCl exceeding 100% can be attributed to a combination of factors, including potential overestimation in ICP-OES measurements, underestimation of the total Ca content in the raw material, or minor contamination from reagents or equipment. These factors can lead to apparent recoveries that surpass the actual Ca content present in the original sample. The similar recovery trends observed for both PG types suggest that both materials respond comparably to these solvents. However, slight differences in recovery efficiency may reflect variations in

their mineralogical composition, which could influence the solubility of Ca during leaching (Bourgier, 2007).

Figure 19. Ca recovery (%) from CrG and FG samples, leached with 1 M solvents as a function of L/S ratio (ml/g), based on ICP-OES and SEM-EDS data

5.3.4 Morphological changes in solid residues

This chapter presents a comparative analysis of the morphological changes observed in the solid residues from the leaching experiments for the two different PG types. The morphological characteristics of the solid residues are also compared to those of the original gypsum raw material. To illustrate the differences effectively, SEM-EDS images captured at a magnification of 500x of the samples leached at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g were selected. It is important to note that no SEM-EDS images are available for the samples leached with 1 M HCl, as the PG was completely dissolved under these conditions.

Figure 20 displays the morphological differences between the solid residues of FG and CrG after leaching with H₂O. When comparing the solid residues to the SEM-EDS images of the raw material, it is evident that the particles have been broken down and are smaller. Furthermore, the FG particles appear smaller and more compact compared to the CrG sample, which exhibits larger, fibrous structures. Additionally, an octagon shape can be observed in the SEM-EDS image of the CrG sample. Through elemental analysis, it could be identified that it contains Ca, F, and Al.

Figure 20. SEM-EDS images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with H_2O at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 21 presents SEM-EDS images of CrG and the FG solid samples after leaching with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 . Consistent with previous observations, the FG particles remain smaller and more compact than those of CrG. When comparing the CrG residues leached with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 to those leached with H_2O , the particles appear more fragmented and feathery, indicating a higher degree of structural breakdown, which may suggest enhanced dissolution. However, based on the mass loss calculations, there are negligible differences between the two solid samples. In Contrast, the FG sample leached with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 exhibits morphological features similar to those observed in the untreated raw material, implying limited structural change under these conditions, which is consistent with the mass loss calculations.

Figure 21. SEM-EDS images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 22 presents the resulting SEM-EDS images of the CrG and FG samples leached with 0.1 M CA. Compared to the samples leached with 0.1 M H₂SO₄, the morphological differences are relatively minor. However, the particles in both CrG and FG samples appear notably less feathery, indicating a somewhat reduced degree of surface degradation or fragmentation.

Figure 22. SEM images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 0.1 M CA at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 23 presents the morphological characteristics of the CrG and FG samples after leaching with 1 M NH₃. Compared to the previously analysed solid residues, these samples exhibit fewer feathery features and instead display sharper, needle-like structures. This suggests a lower degree of structural degradation. The relatively mild morphological alterations are consistent with the lower leaching efficiency observed for both P and Ca, as well as the low mass loss. These findings indicate that the limited chemical interaction between NH₃ and the gypsum matrix results in less pronounced morphological changes, which aligns with the recovery data and supports the interpretation of NH₃ as a less effective leaching agent for both elements.

Figure 23. SEM images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 1 M NH_3 at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 24 presents SEM-EDS images of CrG and FG residues following leaching with 0.1 M HCl. Compared to the untreated raw materials, the particles appear smaller and exhibit a more feathery, blown-out morphology, indicating structural alterations. When comparing the two samples, the CrG residue displays finer particles than the FG residue. Interestingly, the octahedral structure previously observed in the CrG sample leached with H_2O is also present in this sample, suggesting the persistence or reformation of specific mineral phases. Morphologically, the CrG particles resemble those observed in the 0.1 M H_2SO_4 leaching experiments, indicating similar degradation behaviour under both acidic conditions.

Figure 24. SEM-EDS images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 0.1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 25 presents the SEM-EDS images of the CrG and FG solid residues following leaching with 1 M NH_4Cl . Compared to the previous SEM-EDS images, these appear

noticeably darker, which may be attributed to the underlying carbon tape becoming visible due to reduced sample coverage or thinner residue layers. Interestingly, despite the high mass loss and efficient Ca leaching observed with NH_4Cl , the particles exhibit sharper, needle-like structures. This suggests that while NH_4Cl effectively dissolves specific components, it may also promote the formation or preservation of crystalline features in the remaining solid matrix.

Figure 25. SEM-EDS images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 1 M NH_4Cl at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 26 presents SEM-EDS images of CrG and FG solid residues following leaching with 1 M H_2SO_4 . Compared to the solid residues obtained from leaching with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 (Fig.21), the overall morphology appears largely similar, with only minor differences such as slightly smaller and more feathery particle structures. These subtle changes suggest that increasing the acid concentration only moderately affects the surface morphology of the solid residues. This may indicate that the dissolution mechanism is not strongly influenced by acid strength alone, and that variations in morphology are more likely to depend on the type of solvent used rather than its concentration. However, further investigations across a broader range of concentrations would be needed to confirm these observations.

Figure 26. SEM-EDS images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 1 M H_2SO_4 at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Figure 27 shows SEM-EDS images of CrG and FG solid residues after leaching with 1 M CA. Compared to the corresponding residues from leaching with 0.1 M CA (Fig.22), similar morphological features are observed, consistent with those observed in H_2SO_4 -leached samples. This suggests that increasing the concentration of CA induces only minor alterations in the surface morphology. The chelating nature of CA, which allows it to form stable complexes with metal ions such as Ca (Barrow, Debnath and Sen, 2018), may influence dissolution behaviour without significantly altering the solid structure.

Figure 27. SEM-EDS images of solid residues from CrG and FG samples after leaching with 1 M CA at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

5.4 Mass balance evaluation

To verify the accuracy of the leaching experiments, a mass balance evaluation was performed, as shown in Table 8. This analysis was essential for assessing the reliability of the P and Ca recovery data across the different leaching conditions. The mass balance was calculated by comparing the total amount of each element introduced with the sum of the recovered fractions in both the solid and liquid phases after leaching. Table 8 presents the mass balance data for Ca and P in the CrG samples, calculated for the two most promising L/S ratios: 100 and 50 ml/g. It includes mass losses as well as the distribution of each element in the solid and liquid fractions, providing insight into the leaching efficiency and material dissolution under each condition. Detailed calculations are provided in Appendix C. Liquid-phase analyses were conducted using ICP-OES, and solid-phase analyses using SEM-EDS.

Closed mass balances, defined as total recoveries approaching 100%, were generally observed. However, notable exceptions occurred in the P balances for 1 M HCl and NH₃ at both L/S ratios, as well as for NH₄Cl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g. In the NH₃ experiments, P recovery in the liquid phase was consistently zero, a result that was confirmed by UV-vis spectroscopy. This raised questions regarding where the P resides, as it was neither detected in the liquid fraction nor fully accounted for in the solid fraction. One possible explanation is precipitated below detection limits or the formation of undetected complexes.

In the HCl systems, P mass balance closure ranged between 60% and 80%, indicating an incomplete balance. For NH₄Cl, at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, 15% of P was recovered in the solid fraction and 39% in the liquid fraction. These discrepancies suggest either losses during sample handling or the presence of species not quantified by the analytical techniques. These factors not only affect mass balance closure but may also impact the reproducibility, as they can lead to inconsistent recovery results.

An additional anomaly was observed in the 0.1 M HCl experiment at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, where Ca recovery exceeded 100%. Specifically, 126% of Ca was detected in the liquid phase, with an additional 6% detected in the solid fraction. This over-

recovery may be attributed to analytical overestimation, contamination, or calibration drift in the ICP instrument.

Finally, the calculated mass losses can be compared to the mass balances to assess their interrelationship. The highest mass losses were observed in samples leached at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g using 1 M HCl and NH₄Cl, with losses of 93% and 83%, respectively. A similar high loss of 76% was observed for 1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g. These large losses suggest significant dissolution, consistent with the high concentrations of P and Ca detected in the liquid phases for these samples.

Table 6. Mass balance evaluation (%) for Ca and P under L/S ratios of 100 and 50 ml/g, based on ICP-OES and SEM-EDS analysis of liquid and solid fractions of CrG samples.

			H ₂ O	H ₂ SO ₄	H ₂ SO ₄	HCl	HCl	CA	CA	NH ₃	NH ₄ Cl	
				0.1M	1M	0.1M	1M	0.1M	1M	1M	1M	
L/S =50 ml/g	Mass loss	%	15	11	15	22	76	14	16	15	41	
	Ca	Solid out	%	91	92	91	81	26	97	85	96	59
		Liquid out	%	12	11	16	29	86	15	21	8	43
	P	Solid out	%	85	42	59	37	16	57	60	91	44
		Liquid out	%	16	40	52	53	56	36	45	0	19
	L/S =100 ml/g	Mass loss	%	27	25	25	62	93	34	38	33	83
Ca		Solid out	%	78	77	78	41	7	62	62	70	15
		Liquid out	%	31	30	33	70	126	43	41	20	94
P		Solid out	%	72	41	54	20	6	36	35	71	15
		Liquid out	%	28	58	57	62	61	54	48	0	39

5.5 Comparative evaluation of solvent performance

Building on the mass balance evaluation in Section 5.4, which confirmed the reliability of the recovery data for most solvents and conditions, this section presents a comparative analysis of the solvent performance to identify the most effective and selective leaching agents for Ca and P recovery across both CrG and FG.

The leaching experiments demonstrated that solvent chemistry, concentration, and L/S ratio significantly influenced the recovery of P and Ca from both PG sources. Among all tested conditions, 1 M HCl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g consistently yielded the highest overall dissolution efficiency. P recovery reached approximately 95% in the FG sample and 70% in the CrG sample, while Ca recovery exceeded 100% in both samples. As noted in Section 5.4, these apparent over-recoveries are interpreted as analytical artefacts, likely caused by matrix effect, calibration drift, or overestimation in ICP-OES measurements. Despite these artefacts, the superior performance of HCl can be attributed to its high proton activity, which promotes phosphate mineral breakdown and chloride complexation, stabilising Ca in the solution. This aligns with findings by Bouargane, Laaboubi, *et al.*, (2023), who reported that chloride ions enhance Ca solubility while facilitating efficient P release. A summary of the most efficient solvents and conditions, based on their ability to dissolve and selectively separate Ca and P, are presented in Table 7.

1 M NH₄Cl at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g demonstrated the highest potential for selective Ca recovery, achieving nearly complete Ca dissolution (90-100%) while limiting P solubility to 20-40%. Although co-dissolution of P still occurred, NH₄Cl outperformed the other solvents in terms of selectivity, representing a promising direction for optimising Ca-P separation. Nevertheless, further optimisation is required, as current co-dissolution levels remain too high to yield an ultrapure gypsum phase.

Table 7. Summary of the most effective solvents and conditions, based on their ability to dissolve and selectively separate Ca and P. The mass (%) of each element in the liquid phases is based on ICP-OES.

Criteria	Solvent & conditions	Recovery in FG	Recovery in CrG	Notes
Best solvent for P	1 M HCl, L/S ratio 100 ml/g	P: 95%	P: 70%	Also dissolves Ca simultaneously
Best solvent for Ca	1 M HCl, L/S ratio 100 ml/g	Ca: 120%	Ca: 120%	Also dissolves P simultaneously
Best selective solvent	1 M NH ₄ Cl, L/S ratio 100 ml/g	Ca: 100%, P: 20%	Ca: 90%, P: 40%	Promising for Ca-P separation, optimisation needed
Difference between CrG and FG	All solvents	Comparable trends	Comparable trends	Comparable trends, minor differences at higher recoveries

Overall, FG and CrG responded similarly across solvents and operational conditions, with only minor differences. This suggests that leaching strategies are transferable across PG sources, possibly reducing the need for separate feedstock in a future valorisation process. The slight differences observed in P recovery are likely attributed to subtle compositional variations in the PG matrix. This aligns with literature, as studies indicate that PG origin and the phosphoric acid process influence the impurity profile (European Fertilizer Manufacturers, 2000; Binnemans *et al.*, 2015; Bilal *et al.*, 2023). The REE content in both PG types would be of interest to analyse in future studies, as their content can vary depending on the PG origin. Additionally, quantifying the distribution of REEs under different leaching regimes is critical, as their recovery is central to the economic and environmental feasibility of PG valorisation (Gasser *et al.*, 2022).

5.6 Comparison of analytical techniques

Accurate quantification of P and Ca was essential for assessing the efficiency of the leaching process and validating the material recovery. To enhance the reliability of the

results, multiple independent analytical techniques were compared. This approach was employed to identify potential systematic errors and to ensure that observed trends were not artefacts of a single method, thereby strengthening the credibility of the findings.

In this study, a comparison of the results of the analytical techniques was performed by evaluating the mass balance calculations (%) based on the different analytical techniques. ICP-OES was used for liquid phase analysis, while EDTA titration was applied for Ca analysis in the liquid phase, and UV-vis for P analysis in the liquid phase. SEM-EDS was employed for solid-phase analysis across all samples. The mass percentages of the elements in the raw materials were assumed to be 100%, and mass balances were calculated by summing the percentages of elements recovered in both solid and liquid phases. These comparisons were conducted on CrG samples with an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g. The results for the P mass balances are presented in Figure 28, and the Ca mass balances in Figure 29.

STDs for each analyte were attributed to the analytical method used for quantification of the element in the liquid phase. ICP-OES uncertainties were based on instrument precision and calibration reproducibility, while EDTA titration and UV-Vis were evaluated based on procedural repeatability and detection limits. The detection limits for EDTA titration were constrained by the sensitivity of the colorimetric endpoints, typically in the low ppm range, while UV-Vis detection limits were determined by instrument sensitivity and analyte absorptivity.

For P mass balances, UV-Vis and ICP-OES generally yielded comparable results, with minor deviations. Notably, in the experiment using 1 M NH_4Cl , UV-Vis failed to detect P, whereas ICP-OES reported a recovery of approximately 40%. This discrepancy accounts for the 20% deviation in the mass balance and is likely caused by limitations in the MB method in combination with UV-vis. Overall, P mass balances range from 80-90%, indicating a good accuracy and strong agreement between methods. STDs were generally low, supporting the precision of the measurements. The ICP-OES result indicating 80% P recovery using 1 M HCl as solvent was unexpected, considering that the entire PG sample was fully dissolved in the acidic medium, leaving no solid residue. This discrepancy suggests that the actual

P recovery may have been underestimated, potentially due to matrix interference or calibration inaccuracies affecting the measurement.

For Ca mass balances, ICP-OES consistently yielded higher recovery values than EDTA titration, with an average difference of approximately 10%. This discrepancy is likely due to subjective interpretation during the colorimetric endpoint detection in the EDTA titration, which may have led to a slight underestimation of Ca concentrations. However, the difference was consistent across samples. Both techniques are considered reliable for comparative purposes. Nevertheless, careful attention to the colour change at the endpoint is recommended to minimise operator-induced variability and to improve accuracy.

Figure 28. Comparison of P mass balances (%) for samples with an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g. ICP-OES and UV-Vis were used for quantification of P in the liquid phase, while SEM-EDS was employed for analysis of the solid phase.

Figure 29. Comparison of Ca mass balances (%) for samples with an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g. ICP-OES and EDTA titrations were used for quantification of P in the liquid phase, while SEM-EDS was employed for analysis of the solid phase.

Despite these deviations, the overall alignment of the datasets from the different analytical routes supports the validity of the experimental findings, confirming that both the leaching trends and elemental recoveries are reliable. The detailed calculations supporting these findings are presented in Appendix D.

For future applications, ICP-OES is recommended as the primary method due to its ability to analyse all solvent systems, including NH_4Cl and CA solutions, and its capacity to detect multiple elements beyond Ca and P. While EDTA titration and UV-Vis spectroscopy are more cost-effective and suitable for routine analysis, they showed limitations in specific systems: EDTA titration could not be applied to CA-leached samples, and UV-Vis failed to detect P in NH_4Cl - and CA-leached samples. Therefore, ICP-OES offers the most robust and versatile option, especially when working with complex matrices or aiming for broader elemental analysis.

6 Conclusions

This study investigated the selective separation of P and Ca from two types of PG, one sedimentary and one magmatic. The objective was to obtain an ultrapure gypsum phase suitable for CaCO_3 synthesis, while simultaneously investigating the recovery and valorisation of P. A second objective was to compare the leaching behaviour of the two PG types to assess their comparability. A range of analytical techniques, including UV-Vis spectroscopy, EDTA titration, ICP-OES, and SEM-EDS, was employed to quantify Ca and P. In addition, the performance of these analytical methods was compared.

Leaching experiments were conducted using various solvents (HCl, H_2SO_4 , CA, NH_4Cl , NH_3 , and H_2O) across varying L/S ratios: 100, 50, 20, and 10 ml/g. A set of experiments was performed in triplicate, confirming reproducibility. A leaching time of 2 hours was selected based on the pH measurements, which showed stabilization within that time period. Several operational parameters were evaluated for their influence on leaching efficiency. Elevated temperatures (30, 50, and 70°C) enhanced P recovery, with 50°C yielding a 10-15 % increase compared to 30°C . This suggests that 50°C offers a favourable balance between recovery efficiency and energy demand. However, further investigation is needed as temperature effects were only studied on a limited number of samples.

The experiments revealed consistent trends between the two PG types, suggesting that mineralogical differences play a minor role in separation efficiency and that results between the two PG types are largely comparable. An L/S ratio of 100 ml/g consistently yielded the highest recovery rates and mass loss, indicating improved mass transfer and dissolution kinetics at higher solvent volumes. Samples leached at lower L/S ratios followed similar proportional trends across all solvents, suggesting that while increased solvent volume enhances leaching efficiency, the relative effectiveness of each solvent remains consistent. Similarly, higher solvent concentrations at 1 M consistently outperformed their 0.1 M counterparts in terms of both Ca and P recovery, suggesting that 1 M solutions are preferable for efficient

leaching. Future studies could explore concentrations above 1 M to assess whether further improvements are achievable.

Among the tested solvents, 1 M HCl yielded the highest recovery rates for both Ca and P, with P recovery reaching 95% in FG and 90% in CrG, and CA recovery exceeding 100% in both PG types at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g. However, HCl solubilised both elements into the same phase, limiting selective separation. NH₄Cl demonstrated potential for selective separation of Ca, with Ca recovery above 100% in FG and 95% in CrG, at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g. Nevertheless, residual P content remained too high to meet the purity requirements for the gypsum phase, with P recovery around 30% in FG and 40% in CrG. The high efficiency of HCl and NH₄Cl can be attributed to the formation of Ca-chloride complexes, which enhance Ca solubility in the PG. The ratio between Ca and P in the samples varied depending on solvent type, indicating that solvent chemistry plays a key role in separation efficiency.

Mass balance evaluations confirmed closed balances in most cases, though some discrepancies were observed. These may be attributed to sample handling losses, analytical limitations, or the presence of unquantified species. Such factors can affect both mass balance closure and reproducibility, potentially leading to inconsistent recovery results. Over-recoveries of certain elements may reflect analytical overestimation or contamination.

Analytical comparisons showed that UV-Vis and ICP-OES provided consistent results for P quantification in most samples. However, UV-Vis failed to detect P in CA and NH₄Cl samples, which ICP-OES successfully quantified. EDTA titration and ICP-OES showed good agreement for Ca analysis, with EDTA offering a cost-effective alternative for routine measurements. EDTA-titration was unable to detect Ca in CA samples, possibly due to the formation of complex compounds. Overall, ICP-OES proved to be the most robust and versatile option, especially when working with complex matrices or aiming for broader elemental analysis. However, for routine applications, both EDTA titration and UV-vis remain viable and economical options.

REE leachability was not assessed due to time constraints and lack of instrumentation, future research should address their distribution to evaluate recovery potential. Further optimisation of solvent systems, particularly HCl and NH₄Cl, could enhance the

selective the separation of Ca and P. Additionally, assessing the economic and environmental feasibility of these valorisation methods is essential. Overall, this work contributes to the development of sustainable strategies for PG treatment, offering a pathway toward resource-efficient recovery of critical elements and supporting the transition to circular material flows in the phosphate industry.

7 Svensk sammanfattning

Fosfogips är en industriell biprodukt som genereras vid produktionen av fosforsyra. Fosforsyra används huvudsakligen för att framställa fosforbaserade gödselmedel och produceras genom så kallad "wet digestion" av naturlig fosforit. För varje ton producerad fosforsyra genereras cirka fem ton fosfogips, vilket motsvarar en global årlig produktion på uppskattningsvis 100–280 miljoner ton.

Fosfogips är ett heterogent material som innehåller värdefulla komponenter såsom fosfor, kalcium, sällsynta jordartsmetaller och silikater. Utöver detta innehåller fosfogips även föroreningar och toxiska ämnen. Därför klassificeras det som ett naturlig förekommande radioaktivt material (NORM), vilket medför betydande utmaningar när det gäller återvinning och valorisation av materialet.

För närvarande är den dominerande metoden för hantering av fosfogips deponering i mark, ofta utan förbehandling. Detta medför miljörisker och utgör en av de största utmaningarna inom fosforindustrin. Deponering kan leda till erosion av fosfogipshögar samt utsläpp av skadliga ämnen, vilket i sin tur kan orsaka kontaminering av närliggande mark- och vattenområden. Samtidigt har den globala efterfrågan på fosforbaserade gödselmedel ökat vilket accelererat användningen av icke-förnybara fosforitreserver. Detta understryker vikten av att utveckla metoder för valorisering av fosfogips, både för att minska miljöpåverkan och för att bidra till en mer hållbar och cirkulär fosforkälla.

Denna avhandling har genomförts inom ramen för det EU-finansierade projektet FIC-Fighters, som åtgärdar ovanstående problematik. Projektet fokuserar på valorisering av fosfogips som en hållbar källa för att utvinna kalciumkarbonat, natriumsulfat, ammoniumsulfat, fosfor, samt sällsynta jordartsmetaller. Dessa ämnen har potentiella tillämpningar inom bland annat pappers-, cement-, batteri- och gödselindustrin.

Syftet med denna studie är att undersöka separationen av fosfor och kalcium från två typer av fosfogips, en sedimentär och en magmatisk, genom olika lakningsmetoder. Målet är att framställa en ren mellanprodukt som kan användas i en

karbonatiseringsreaktion för att omvandlas till kalciumkarbonat, i en ammoniakalt eller alkaliskt medium. I processen binds koldioxid och samtidigt möjliggörs valoriseringen av fosfor som lakats ur fosfogipset. Olika analytiska metoder tillämpades för jämförelse samt för att säkerställa trovärdiga resultat.

Lakningsexperimenten genomfördes med både sura och basiska lösningsmedel med koncentrationer på 0,1 M och 1 M. De använda lösningsmedlen inkluderade citronsyra, svavelsyra, saltsyra, ammoniumhydroxid och ammoniumklorid. Försöken utfördes vid vätska-till-fast ämne-förhållanden 100, 50, 20 och 10 ml/g. De analytiska metoder som tillämpades omfattade UV-Vis spektroskopi i kombination med molybdenumblå metoden för analys av fosfor i vätskeprov. Komplexometrisk titrering med EDTA användes för kvantitativ analys av kalcium i vätskeprov. Fasta prover karakteriserades med SEM-EDS och slutligen användes ICP-OES för validering och multielementanalys av vätskeprov. Ytterligare experimentella parametrar inkluderade mätning av pH och elektrisk konduktivitet, samt bedömning av reproducerbarhet genom experiment som utfördes i triplikat. Temperaturvariationer studerades genom att utföra lakning med 1 M saltsyra vid 30, 50 och 70°C.

Resultaten för lakningen av fosfor och kalcium indikerade att de geologiska skillnaderna mellan de två gipsen är försumbara. Därmed är resultaten mellan de två fosfogipsen jämförelsebara. Vidare visade resultaten att vätska-till-fast ämne-förhållande 100 ml/g gav de högsta återvinningsgraderna för kalcium och fosfor, vilket tyder på effektivare masstransport och upplösningskinetik vid högre volymer. Förhöjda temperaturer, särskilt 50°C, visade sig ytterligare främja återvinningen av fosfor. Dock kräver detta ytterligare undersökning eftersom det inte analyserades mer ingående. Lakning av både kalcium och fosfor förbättrades vid högre lösningsmedelskoncentrationer, där 1 M koncentrationer konsekvent gav bättre resultat än 0,1 M koncentrationer. Ytterligare forskning med koncentrationer över 1 M kan vara värdefullt för att bedöma ifall effektivare lakning kan uppnås vid de förhållandena.

Bland de testade lösningsmedlen visade 1 M saltsyra vara mest effektiv för lakning av både kalcium och fosfor. Lakningseffektiviteten för kalcium samt fosfor uppgick till cirka 100%, enligt analys med ICP-OES och UV-Vis spektroskopi. Däremot visade

ICP-OES analys ett lägre fosforåtervinningsvärde på cirka 60%, vilket indikerar viss variation beroende på den analytiska metoden. Trots de höga återvinningsgraderna resulterade denna metod i att båda elementen löstes i samma fas, vilket begränsade möjligheten för selektiv separation. Ammoniumklorid visade däremot god selektivitet för kalcium och uppnådde en återvinningsgrad på cirka 95%, baserat på ICP-OES analys. Fosforutlakningen kunde konstateras försumbar eftersom UV-Vis spektroskopi visade resultat på 0%. Dock indikerade ICP-OES analysen att fosforåtervinningen skulle ligga på ca 40%. Oberoende, tyder dessa resultat på att ammoniumklorid potentiellt kan isolera kalcium utan betydande mängder fosfor. Mera forskning krävs för att säkerställa i vilken grad fosfor lakas ut. Optimeringen är även nödvändig för att nå FIC-Fighters mål att uppnå en ultra-ren kalcium fas.

Utvärdering av massbalanserna visade att resultaten i de flesta fall var konsekventa och tyder på god noggrannhet i experimenten, även om vissa avvikelser förekom. Dessa avvikelser kan bero på förluster vid provhantering, analytiska begränsningar eller förekomsten av ämnen som inte kvantifierats med den använda metoden. Sådana faktorer kan ytterligare påverka experimentens reproducerbarhet, vilken i sin tur kan leda till varierande återvinningsresultat.

Jämförelse av resultaten från UV-Vis spektroskopi samt ICP-OES gav överensstämmande resultat för fosforanalysen i de flesta prov. Däremot kunde UV-Vis spektroskopi inte detektera fosfor i prover som lakats med citronsyra eller ammoniumklorid, vilket ICP-OES kunde. EDTA titrering och ICP-OES visade ytterligare god överensstämmelse vid analys av kalcium, där EDTA titrering erbjuder ett mer kostnadseffektivt alternativ för rutinmässiga mätningar. EDTA-titreringen kunde dock inte detektera kalcium i prover som lakats med citronsyra. På basen av detta kan ICP-OES konstateras vara den mest mångsidiga metoden, särskilt vid undersökning av mer komplexa prov eller vid behov av bredare elementanalys. För rutinmässiga tillämpningar är både EDTA titrering och UV-Vis ekonomiska alternativ.

Framtida forskning bör fokusera på att optimera den selektiva lakningen, speciellt med lösningsmedel som saltsyra och ammoniumklorid. Det kan även vara utav värde att vidare optimera lakningseffektiviteten för svavelsyra, med tanke på att den redan används i fosforsyra produktionen. Ytterligare bör högre koncentrationer samt

effekten av processtekniska parametrar som temperaturen ytterligare optimeras för att förbättra separationseffektiviteten. Dessutom vore undersökning av uppskalningsmöjligheter och energikostnader viktigt för att bedöma framtida praktisk tillämpning. Att kvantifiera distributionen på de sällsynta jordartsmetallerna bundna i fosfogipset och deras återvinningspotential är även av stor vikt, eftersom de inte kunde undersökas i denna studie på grund av tidsbrist samt brist på analytisk apparatur.

8 References

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Appendix A – Mass loss calculations

Table A 1. Mass loss calculations (%) for CrG samples

Solvent	L/S ratio (ml/g)	mass before (g)	mass after (g)	mass loss (%)
H2O	100	5.039	3.675	27
H2O	50	5.009	4.250	15
H2O	20	5.009	4.656	7
H2O	10	5.016	4.818	4
0.1M H2SO4	100	4.999	3.729	25
0.1M H2SO4	50	4.999	4.455	11
0.1M H2SO4	20	5.000	4.710	6
0.1M H2SO4	10	5.009	4.761	5
0.1M HCl	100	5.013	1.888	62
0.1M HCl	50	5.006	3.914	22
0.1M HCl	20	5.008	4.363	13
0.1M HCl	10	5.000	4.826	3
0.1M CA	100	5.006	3.314	34
0.1M CA	50	5.026	4.345	14
0.1M CA	20	5.013	4.600	8
0.1M CA	10	5.013	7.018	
1M H2SO4	100	5.022	3.733	26
1M H2SO4	50	5.001	4.241	15
1M H2SO4	20	5.000	4.605	8
1M H2SO4	10	5.008	4.640	7
1M HCl	100	5.028	0.323	94
1M HCl	50	5.004	1.188	76
1M HCl	20	5.014	3.385	32
1M HCl	10	5.020	3.962	21
1M CA	100	5.009	3.098	38
1M CA	50	5.023	4.212	16
1M CA	20	5.035	4.641	8
1M CA	10	5.004	4.822	4
1M NH3	100	5.029	3.351	33
1M NH3	50	5.030	4.287	15
1M NH3	20	5.016	4.606	8
1M NH3	10	5.005	4.899	2
1M NH4Cl	100	5.004	0.838	83
1M NH4Cl	50	5.019	2.950	41
1M NH4Cl	20	5.033	4.335	14
1M NH4Cl	10	5.022	4.479	11

Table A 2. Mass loss calculations (%) for FG samples

Solvent	L/S ratio (ml/g)	mass before (g)	mass after (g)	mass loss (%)
H ₂ O	100	5.001	3.510	30
H ₂ O	50	5.003	4.256	15
H ₂ O	20	5.001	4.656	7
H ₂ O	10	5.001	4.691	6
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	100	5.000	3.628	27
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	50	5.000	4.241	15
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	20	5.009	4.621	8
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	10	5.006	4.717	6
0.1M HCl	100	5.007	1.928	61
0.1M HCl	50	5.010	3.340	33
0.1M HCl	20	5.018	4.210	16
0.1M HCl	10	5.003	4.534	9
0.1M CA	100	5.005	3.499	30
0.1M CA	50	5.000	4.332	13
0.1M CA	20	5.001	4.833	3
0.1M CA	10	4.991	4.933	1
1M H ₂ SO ₄	100	5.003	3.389	32
1M H ₂ SO ₄	50	5.003	4.281	14
1M H ₂ SO ₄	20	5.000	4.747	5
1M H ₂ SO ₄	10	5.003	4.752	5
1M HCl	100	5.007	0.071	99
1M HCl	50	5.018	0.169	97
1M HCl	20	5.017	3.432	32
1M HCl	10	5.008	4.223	16
1M CA	100	5.010	3.227	36
1M CA	50	5.004	4.297	14
1M CA	20	5.004	5.168	
1M CA	10	5.003	5.065	
1M NH ₃	100	5.007	3.226	36
1M NH ₃	50	5.014	4.003	20
1M NH ₃	20	5.001	4.296	14
1M NH ₃	10	5.001	4.472	11
1M NH ₄ Cl	100	5.015	0.277	94
1M NH ₄ Cl	50	5.004	2.803	44
1M NH ₄ Cl	20	5.007	4.046	19
1M NH ₄ Cl	10	5.013	4.310	14

Table A 3. Mass loss calculations (%) for the replicated samples with 0.1 M H₂SO₄

Trial	L/S ratio (ml/g)	mass before (g)	mass after (g)	mass loss (%)
Trial 1	100	5	3.63	27.45
Trial 1	50	5	4.24	15.20
Trial 1	20	5.009	4.62	7.76
Trial 1	10	5.0059	4.72	5.78
Trial 2	100	5.0004	3.20	36.04
Trial 2	50	5.0067	4.05	19.14
Trial 2	20	5.00324	4.56	8.90
Trial 2	10	5.00234	4.61	7.88
Trial 3	100	5.0054	3.46	30.86
Trial 3	50	5.009	4.10	18.24
Trial 3	20	5.00589	4.52	9.66
Trial 3	10	5.00632	4.65	7.12

Table A 4. Mass loss calculations (%) for 1 M HCl samples done at different temperatures

Gypsum	Temperature (°C)	mass before (g)	mass after (g)	mass loss (%)
CrG	30	5.0223	0.0692	98.62
CrG	50	5.0069	0.0397	99.21
CrG	70	5.0021	0.0891	98.22
FG	30	5.0272	-0.0087	100.17
FG	50	5.073	0.0025	99.95
FG	70	5.0193	-0.0123	100.25

Appendix B - Calculation of P concentrations from UV-vis measurements

Table B 1. P concentration displayed in both mg/l and mmol/l in the samples analysed with UV-vis. The dilution made for each sample for the analysis is presented. The amount of recovered P (%) for each sample has been calculated based on the SEM-EDS data, which suggests the CrG raw material contains 3646.15 mg/kg P.

Sample	V _{sample} (l)	C (diluted sample)	Mass (kg)	Absorbance	C. after MB dilution	C. Before dilution (mg/l)	Conc. P (mmol/l)	Recovered amount of P (%)
CrG1	0.5	(1:5)	0.005	0.65	2.26	11.28	0.36	30.71
CrG2	0.25	(1:5)	0.005	0.90	3.64	18.21	0.59	24.93
CrG3	0.1	(1:10)	0.005	0.88	3.53	35.29	1.14	19.32
CrG4	0.05	(1:10)	0.005	0.94	3.81	38.12	1.23	10.42
CrG5	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.49	1.41	14.10	0.46	38.49
CrG6	0.25	(1:10)	0.005	0.87	3.47	34.71	1.12	47.60
CrG7	0.1	(1:10)	0.005	1.11	4.75	47.47	1.53	26.03
CrG8	0.05	(1:10)	0.005	1.30	5.76	57.59	1.86	15.77
CrG9	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.60	2.00	20.03	0.65	54.94
CrG10	0.25	(1:10)	0.005	0.99	4.11	41.08	1.33	56.35
CrG11	0.1	(1:20)	0.005	0.91	3.65	72.92	2.35	40.00
CrG12	0.05	(1:83)	0.005	0.62	2.09	173.07	5.59	47.39
CrG21	0.5		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG22	0.25		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG23	0.1		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG24	0.05		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG13	0.5		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG14	0.25		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG15	0.1		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG16	0.05		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG17	0.5		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG18	0.25		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG19	0.1		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG20	0.05		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG25	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.74	2.78	27.80	0.90	76.06
CrG26	0.25	(1:10)	0.005	1.03	4.29	42.93	1.39	58.42
CrG27	0.1	(1:20)	0.005	1.00	3.80	75.91	2.45	41.57
CrG28	0.05	(1:50)	0.005	0.95	3.87	193.45	6.25	52.65
CrG29	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.78	2.67	26.69	0.86	72.81
CrG30	0.25	(1:20)	0.005	0.71	2.27	45.37	1.47	62.18
CrG31	0.1	(1:50)	0.005	0.71	2.29	114.61	3.70	62.70
CrG32	0.05	(1:50)	0.005	1.05	4.04	202.25	6.53	55.25
CrG33	0.5		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG34	0.25		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG35	0.1		0.005	0.00				0.00
CrG36	0.05		0.005	0.00				0.00

Table B 2. P concentration displayed in both mg/l and mmol/l in the samples analysed with UV-vis. The dilution made for each sample for the analysis is presented. The amount of recovered P (%) for each sample has been calculated based on the SEM-EDS data, which suggests the FG raw material contains 3046.15 mg/kg P.

Sample	V sample (L)	Dilution factor	mass (g)	Absorbance	C. MB dilution	C. Before dilution (mg/l)	C. P (mmol/l)	Recovered amount of P (%)
FG1	0.5	(1:5)	0.005	0.44	1.38	6.88	0.22	22.58
FG2	0.25	(1:5)	0.005	0.65	2.29	11.43	0.37	18.75
FG3	0.1	(1:5)	0.005	1.12	4.31	21.57	0.70	14.16
FG4	0.05	(1:10)	0.005	0.75	2.69	26.89	0.87	8.83
FG9	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.70	2.65	26.53	0.86	87.04
FG10	0.25	(1:10)	0.005	1.02	4.19	41.87	1.35	68.68
FG11	0.1	(1:10)	0.005	0		0.00	0.00	0.00
FG12	0.05	(1:10)	0.005	0		0.00	0.00	0.00
FG5	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.67	2.49	24.94	0.81	81.89
FG6	0.25	(1:10)	0.005	0.80	3.11	31.08	1.00	51.02
FG7	0.1	(1:20)	0.005	1.12	4.70	94.02	3.04	61.62
FG8	0.05	(1:83)	0.005	1.01	4.00	331.88	10.72	108.82
FG21	0.5		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG22	0.25		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG23	0.1		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG24	0.05		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG13	0.5		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG14	0.25		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG15	0.1		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG16	0.05		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG17	0.5		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG18	0.25		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG19	0.1		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG20	0.05		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG25	0.5	(1:5)	0.005	0.86	3.21	16.03	0.52	52.55
FG26	0.25	(1:5)	0.005	1.12	4.54	22.69	0.73	37.13
FG27	0.1	(1:10)	0.005	1.13	4.61	46.05	1.49	30.23
FG28	0.05	(1:20)	0.005	1.28	5.38	107.63	3.48	35.33
FG29	0.5	(1:10)	0.005	0.80	2.91	29.12	0.94	95.47
FG30	0.25	(1:20)	0.005	0.73	2.56	51.15	1.65	83.65
FG31	0.1	(1:20)	0.005	1.30	5.48	109.69	3.54	71.78
FG32	0.05	(1:50)	0.005	0.94	3.63	181.51	5.86	59.49
FG33	0.5		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG34	0.25		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG35	0.1		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00
FG36	0.05		0.005			0.00	0.00	0.00

Appendix C – Mass balance calculations

Normalised mass balance calculations for CrG and FG samples at L/S ratios of 100 and 50 ml/g. The mass in the solid phase was estimated from SEM-EDS analysis, while mass in the liquid phase was quantified using ICP-OES.

Table C 1. Normalised mass balance calculations for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g. The initial content of each element is assumed to be 100%.

Solvent	Element	Mass in input (%)	Mass in solid (%)	Mass in liquid (%)	Mass balance
H ₂ O	Ca	100	90.73	11.64	102.37
	P	100	66.06	16.44	82.50
	S	100	84.94	16.23	101.17
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	91.88	10.60	102.48
	P	100	42.06	40.47	82.53
	S	100	84.98	27.78	112.75
0.1M HCl	Ca	100	81.12	29.22	110.33
	P	100	36.91	47.14	84.04
	S	100	78.27	39.35	117.63
0.1M CA	Ca	100	96.86	14.85	111.71
	P	100	57.20	35.94	93.13
	S	100	95.21	18.41	113.62
1M NH ₃	Ca	100	96.44	7.56	104.01
	P	100	91.05	0.00	91.05
	S	100	90.58	14.07	104.65
1M HCl	Ca	100	25.78	95.92	121.70
	P	100	16.29	53.48	69.76
	S	100	24.33	159.60	183.93
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	91.36	16.63	107.98
	P	100	59.00	58.10	117.10
	S	100	88.45	417.20	505.66
1M CA	Ca	100	84.49	21.16	105.65
	P	100	60.41	51.24	111.65
	S	100	83.22	27.32	110.55
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	100	58.66	43.18	101.84
	P	100	43.80	19.57	63.37
	S	100	61.59	68.71	130.30

Table C 2. Normalised mass balance calculations for FG samples at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g. The initial content of each element is assumed to be 100%.

Solvent	Element	Mass in input (%)	Mass in solid (%)	Mass in liquid (%)	Mass balance
H ₂ O	Ca	100	80.89	13.03	93.91
	P	100	45.17	19.15	64.32
	S	100	78.74	0.00	78.74
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	81.73	10.94	92.67
	P	100	0.00	61.56	61.56
	S	100	84.55	35.68	120.22
0.1M HCl	Ca	100	78.78	42.88	121.66
	P	100	91.72	36.12	127.84
	S	100	79.68	231.56	311.24
0.1M CA	Ca	100	84.43	14.13	98.56
	P	100	0.00	44.55	44.55
	S	100	81.65	19.63	101.27
1M NH ₃	Ca	100	80.29	6.73	87.02
	P	100	101.89	0.00	101.89
	S	100	80.30	13.10	93.40
1M HCl	Ca	100	0.00	94.39	94.39
	P	100	0.00	72.26	72.26
	S	100	0.00	200.93	200.93
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	83.31	17.01	100.32
	P	100	56.85	70.15	127.00
	S	100	85.83	340.74	426.58
1M CA	Ca	100	76.93	19.66	96.58
	P	100	71.30	49.42	120.73
	S	100	77.66	31.91	109.58
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	100	49.22	44.01	93.23
	P	100	62.39	5.35	67.74
	S	100	49.01	78.40	127.41

Table C 3. Normalised mass balance calculations for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g. The initial content of each element is assumed to be 10 %.

Solvent	Element	Mass in input (%)	Mass in solid (%)	Mass in Liquid (%)	Mass balance
H ₂ O	Ca	100	78.16	31.42	109.58
	P	100	72.48	27.58	100.06
	S	100	74.56	54.12	128.67
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	76.70	30.30	107.00
	P	100	40.77	58.41	99.18
	S	100	77.60	226.55	304.15
0.1M HCl	Ca	100	40.65	69.70	110.35
	P	100	19.65	62.21	81.86
	S	100	38.51	116.48	154.99
0.1M CA	Ca	100	62.14	43.37	105.51
	P	100	36.19	53.84	90.02
	S	100	61.58	75.71	137.29
1M NH ₃	Ca	100	69.74	20.15	89.88
	P	100	70.53	0.00	70.53
	S	100	62.48	32.21	94.68
1M HCl	Ca	100	6.77	125.79	132.56
	P	100	5.59	60.75	66.34
	S	100	6.42	206.87	213.30
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	77.87	33.19	111.06
	P	100	53.55	57.15	110.70
	S	100	75.20	368.62	443.82
1M CA	Ca	100	61.76	41.06	102.83
	P	100	35.34	48.19	83.53
	S	100	60.16	52.84	113.00
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	100	14.67	94.30	108.97
	P	100	15.40	39.26	54.66
	S	100	14.09	137.83	151.92

Table C 4. Normalised mass balance calculations for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g. The initial content of each element is assumed to be 100%.

Solvent	Element	Mass in input (%)	Mass in solid (%)	Mass in Liquid (%)	Mass balance
H ₂ O	Ca	100	75.57	27.57	103.14
	P	100	93.05	23.09	116.14
	S	100	71.86	59.00	130.86
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	71.72	28.27	100.00
	P	100	19.19	49.86	69.05
	S	100	71.61	234.45	306.06
0.1M HCl	Ca	100	41.18	58.97	100.15
	P	100	51.74	28.12	79.85
	S	100	39.88	120.79	160.67
0.1M CA	Ca	100	65.45	34.91	100.36
	P	100	67.14	44.39	111.53
	S	100	64.66	89.76	154.42
1M NH ₃	Ca	100	59.71	20.57	80.28
	P	100	79.08	0.00	79.08
	S	100	51.16	41.35	92.51
1M HCl	Ca	100	3.13	106.64	109.77
	P	100	10.92	21.59	32.51
	S	100	3.23	207.66	210.89
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	100	0.00	123.50	123.50
	P	100	0.00	62.40	62.40
	S	100	0.00	257.31	257.31
1M CA	Ca	100	64.45	34.21	98.66
	P	100	51.65	55.81	107.47
	S	100	64.44	622.75	687.19
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	100	62.09	38.35	100.44
	P	100	59.45	44.22	103.67
	S	100	60.56	64.66	125.23

Experimental-based mass balance calculations for CrG and FG at L/S ratios of 100 and 50 ml/g. The initial element content in the raw material and the remaining mass in the solid residues was determined using SEM-EDS. The content in the liquid phase was quantified using ICP-OES.

Table C 5. Experimental-based mass balance calculations for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Solvent	Element	Mass Input (mg)	Mass Solid (mg)	Mass Liquid (mg)	Mass balance (%)	STD (%)
H ₂ O	Ca	1297.78	1177.47	151.06	102.37	1.61
	P	20.16	13.32	3.32	82.50	18.21
	S	1070.78	909.48	173.79	101.17	0.94
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1295.34	1190.18	137.25	102.48	1.82
	P	20.12	8.46	8.14	82.53	1.04
	S	1068.77	908.20	296.86	112.75	1.07
0.1M HCl	Ca	1296.95	1052.03	378.95	110.33	2.16
	P	20.15	7.44	9.50	84.04	2.31
	S	1070.10	837.59	421.12	117.63	0.73
0.1M CA	Ca	1302.31	1261.47	193.41	111.71	0.81
	P	20.23	11.57	7.27	93.13	0.05
	S	1074.52	1023.02	197.81	113.62	0.64
1M NH ₃	Ca	1303.25	1256.89	98.57	104.01	1.47
	P	20.25	18.43	0.00	91.05	11.05
	S	1075.29	974.03	151.30	104.65	2.45
1M HCl	Ca	1296.43	334.27	1243.49	121.70	2.75
	P	20.14	3.28	10.77	69.76	17.54
	S	1069.67	260.28	1707.15	183.93	3.68
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1295.63	1183.67	215.42	157.86	2.34
	P	20.13	11.87	11.69	291.42	14.43
	S	1069.01	945.58	4459.93	1757.27	1.32
1M CA	Ca	1301.54	1099.67	275.41	169.13	0.91
	P	20.22	12.21	10.36	265.37	13.81
	S	1073.88	893.72	293.41	192.51	0.66
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	1300.42	762.79	561.51	231.37	3.03
	P	20.20	8.85	3.95	122.09	39.10
	S	1072.96	660.85	737.22	336.43	1.34

Table C 6. Experimental-based mass balance calculations for FG samples at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Solvent	Element	Mass Input (mg)	Mass Solid (mg)	Mass Liquid (mg)	Mass balance (%)	STD (%)
H ₂ O	Ca	1320.51	1068.12	6.34	81.37	1.55
	P	14.93	6.74	1.07	52.34	19.43
	S	1059.68	834.35	200.78	97.68	1.53
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1319.51	1078.46	144.29	92.67	1.13
	P	14.91	0.00	9.18	61.56	0.89
	S	1058.87	895.23	377.78	120.22	0.92
0.1M HCl	Ca	1321.14	1040.77	566.50	121.66	0.94
	P	14.93	13.70	5.39	127.84	17.16
	S	1060.19	844.71	2455.01	311.24	0.91
0.1M CA	Ca	1319.59	1114.15	186.48	140.96	1.60
	P	14.92	0.00	6.64	178.18	0.47
	S	1058.94	864.62	207.82	160.15	1.30
1M NH ₃	Ca	1327.56	1065.89	89.32	87.02	1.63
	P	15.01	15.29	0.00	101.89	0.05
	S	1065.33	855.43	139.61	93.40	2.65
1M HCl	Ca	1324.42	0.00	1250.18	377.58	1.96
	P	14.97	0.00	10.82	289.02	3.89
	S	1062.81	0.00	2135.52	803.72	2.72
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1320.51	1100.07	224.60	151.34	1.08
	P	14.93	8.49	10.47	337.44	20.02
	S	1059.68	909.57	3610.80	1448.81	1.48
1M CA	Ca	1320.75	1016.04	259.60	155.55	1.02
	P	14.93	10.65	7.38	269.00	16.02
	S	1059.87	823.14	338.25	205.32	0.94
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	1320.70	650.08	581.20	225.25	3.85
	P	14.93	9.31	0.80	83.78	17.16
	S	1059.83	519.41	830.94	362.62	3.34

Table C 7. Experimental-based mass balance calculations for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g

Solvent	Element	Mass Input (mg)	Mass Solid (mg)	Mass Liquid (mg)	Mass balance (%)	STD (%)
H ₂ O	Ca	1305.55	1020.37	410.21	141.00	2.23
	P	20.28	14.70	5.59	127.63	15.35
	S	1077.19	803.11	582.96	182.79	1.97
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1295.24	993.40	392.50	137.30	1.50
	P	20.12	8.20	11.75	157.60	18.22
	S	1068.69	829.28	2421.09	530.69	1.62
0.1M HCl	Ca	1298.82	527.94	905.29	180.05	1.71
	P	20.18	3.97	12.55	144.07	19.11
	S	1071.64	412.72	1248.22	271.47	1.41
0.1M CA	Ca	1296.98	805.96	562.44	148.87	1.14
	P	20.15	7.29	10.85	143.86	18.20
	S	1070.12	658.96	810.16	212.99	0.91
1M NH ₃	Ca	1302.94	908.62	262.49	89.88	2.72
	P	20.24	14.28	0.00	70.53	11.15
	S	1075.04	671.64	346.25	94.68	1.50
1M HCl	Ca	1302.68	88.14	1638.65	258.35	1.21
	P	20.24	1.13	12.29	127.09	16.27
	S	1074.82	69.03	2223.53	420.17	1.39
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1301.20	1013.25	431.86	144.25	1.41
	P	20.21	10.82	11.55	167.86	18.95
	S	1073.60	807.34	3957.50	812.44	2.15
1M CA	Ca	1297.83	801.58	532.92	143.89	0.93
	P	20.16	7.13	9.72	131.72	17.42
	S	1070.82	644.20	565.83	165.84	0.70
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	1296.54	190.26	1222.63	203.27	3.38
	P	20.14	3.10	7.91	93.92	13.51
	S	1069.76	150.76	1474.44	289.75	2.39

Table C 8. Experimental-based mass balance calculations for FG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g

Solvent	Element	Mass Input (mg)	Mass in Solid (mg)	Mass Liquid (mg)	Mass balance (%)	STD (%)	
H ₂ O	Ca	1319.92	997.48	363.84	130.70	2.79	
	P	14.92	13.88	3.45	139.23	19.85	
	S	1059.20	761.12	624.94	189.86	2.81	
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1319.67	946.48	373.13	128.27	2.11	
	P	14.92	2.86	7.44	118.91	37.61	
	S	1059.00	758.39	2482.83	540.51	3.38	
0.1M HCl	Ca	1321.44	544.17	779.23	159.12	1.08	
	P	14.94	7.73	4.20	107.97	14.36	
	S	1060.42	422.85	1280.88	281.46	2.27	
0.1M CA	Ca	1320.85	864.50	461.17	135.28	1.68	
	P	14.93	10.02	6.63	155.93	15.83	
	S	1059.95	685.35	951.46	244.19	1.71	
1M NH ₃	Ca	1321.38	789.00	271.86	80.28	2.05	
	P	14.94	11.81	0.00	79.08	14.73	
	S	1060.38	542.45	438.49	92.51	1.94	
1M HCl	Ca	1323.60	41.47	1411.51	216.42	1.98	
	P	14.96	1.63	3.23	54.10	6.66	
	S	1062.16	34.35	2205.68	418.55	1.27	
1M H ₂ SO ₄	Ca	1321.49	0.00	1632.06	247.00	1.30	
	P	14.94	0.00	9.32	124.80	2.75	
	S	1060.46	0.00	2728.65	514.62	1.65	
1M CA	Ca	1320.38	851.02	451.69	132.87	3.81	
	P	14.92	7.71	8.33	163.28	17.41	
	S	1059.57	682.83	6598.43	1309.93	3.37	
1M NH ₄ Cl	Ca	1322.17	820.92	507.05	138.79	1.41	
	H ₂ O	P	14.95	8.88	6.61	147.88	14.48
	S	1061.01	642.60	686.06	189.89	1.48	

Appendix D – Method validation calculations

Table D 1. Comparison of the calcium content (%) between ICP-OES and complexometric titration with EDTA for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Sample	Calcium content mass balance (%)				Comparison of ICP-OES and EDTA (%)
	ICP-OES	STD	EDTA	STD	
H2O	102.37	1.61	104.29	0.85	98.16
0.1M H2SO4	102.48	1.82	110.27	1.37	92.93
1M H2SO4	107.99	2.34	91.36	0.28	118.20
0.1M HCl	110.33	2.16	81.12	0.74	136.02
1M HCl	121.70	2.75	111.87	0.83	108.79
1M NH3	104.01	1.47	96.44	0.42	107.84
1M NH4Cl	101.84	3.03	100.64	0.82	101.19

Table D 2. Comparison of the phosphorus content (%) between ICP-OES and UV-Vis analysis performed with MB method for CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 50 ml/g

Sample	Phosphorus content mass balance (%)				Comparison of ICP-OES and EDTA (%)
	ICP-OES	STD	UV-Vis	STD	
H2O	82.50	18.21	88.64	18.09	93.07
0.1M H2SO4	82.53	1.037	93.10	13.00	88.65
1M H2SO4	117.10	14.41	102.11	19.32	114.68
0.1M HCl	53.29	2.31	60.23	18.60	88.48
1M HCl	69.77	17.54	72.61	13.02	96.08
1M NH3	91.05	11.05	91.05	17.06	100.00
1M NH4Cl	63.38	18.20	43.8	9.33	144.69

Appendix E – Major, minor & trace elements from ICP-OES analysis

Table E 1. Elemental concentrations (mg/l) of selected major, minor and trace elements in leachates obtained from CrG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, analysed by ICP-OES. Values below detection limits are indicated with “<”.

CrG Sample	Si	Al	Cr	Fe	Na	S
H ₂ O	3.95	2.75	0.2	1.81	1.145	1165.916
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	5.895	7	0.2	3.04	1.275	6449.181
1M H ₂ SO ₄	6.71	7.55	<0.0025	1.27	1.305	23984.3
0.1M HCl	5.18	6.65	0.175	3.075	1.21	2496.446
1M HCl	7.505	8	0.8	4.445	1.64	6828.593
0.1 M CA	3.805	4.6	0.15	2.99	1.32	1620.328
1 M CA	4.225	5.2	<0.0025	0.95	0.8	1131.651
1 M NH ₃	3.58	<0.01	<0.0025	0.06	4.555	692.504
1 M NH ₄ Cl	1.98	6.6	0.0275	1.735	0.805	2948.887

Ag, As, B, Ba, Be, Cd, Co, Cu, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Sb, Se, Ti, Zn were below detection limits and are therefore not presented in the table.

Table E 2. Elemental concentrations (mg/l) of selected major, minor and trace elements in leachates obtained from FG samples at an L/S ratio of 100 ml/g, analysed by ICP-OES. Values below detection limits are indicated with “<”.

FG Sample	Si	Al	Cr	Fe	Na	S
H ₂ O	<0.005	0.995	<0.0025	1.17	0.575	189.1
0.1M H ₂ SO ₄	0.35	1.65	1.015	6.495	1.025	6577.651
1M H ₂ SO ₄	<0.005	1.53	<0.0025	2.875	0.51	29212.53
0.1M HCl	<0.005	<0.009	0.135	3.615	0.62	2521.769
1M HCl	0.465	2.35	0.795	8.195	1.17	5462.299
0.1 M CA	<0.005	0.63	0.15	3.48	0.745	1907.916
1 M CA	0.175	1.405	<0.0025	2.3	0.43	1377.122
1 M NH ₃	1.335	0.67	5.605	19.93	1.3	881.975
1 M NH ₄ Cl	1.155	<0.009	<0.0025	<0.0014	5.29	4416.357

Ag, As, B, Ba, Be, Cd, Co, Cu, K, Mg, Mn, Mo, Sb, Se, Ti, Zn were below detection limits and are therefore not presented in the table.